

**THERMAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF
DIFFERENT MULTI LAYER PHASE
CHANGE MATERIALS BASED THERMOCLINE
THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE
SYSTEMS**

by

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- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.

September 2022

মোঃ আলী আজম

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*“Ultimately, education in its real sense is the pursuit of truth.
It is an endless journey through knowledge and enlightenment.”*

Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam

ABSTRACT

A thermocline is a thin transition layer between hot and cold fluid mixture which is generated by thermal difference of the two fluid layers. A thermocline-based thermal energy storage (TES) tank is one of the most important systems for storing thermal energy for concentrating solar power (CSP) plants. The tank usually consists of different types of rocks as filler materials and molten salts as heat transfer media. Hot and cold fluids are stored in the same tank and the fluids are separated because of their thermal stratification. Thus, a temperature gradient is created between the hot and cold fluid zone, which results in a thermocline. In recent era, burning of fossil fuels make us concerned about its harmful effect on environment and long-term impact on climate change. Solar energy, for its abundance in the form of renewable energy becomes attractive source to generate electricity. Researchers paid their attention to find different thermophysical properties of heat transfer fluids (HTF) like alkali fluorides and molten salts as well as thermophysical properties of phase change materials (PCM). High maximum operational temperature, high heat capacity, high thermal conductivity, good sustainability, and low vapor pressure are the desired properties of HTF. Specific heat, latent heat, and the combination of both are the different forms of stored energy in the thermal energy storage (TES) tank. In the present work, the goal is to analyze thermal performance of TES tank and latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) tank numerically for single layered and multi-layered phase change materials (MLPCMs). Molten FLiNaK salt, a eutectic mixture of 46.5% LiF, 11.5% NaF and 42% KF was used as heat transfer media for this scheme. Inorganic salts as well as their mixtures were used as phase change materials. A 2D model of thermocline TES tank was developed which was considered as an isotropic porous medium filled with distinct solid spherical particles. A numerical model was built that describes the way of travelling heat through the thermocline TES tank. Continuity and Momentum equations in porous medium was used for this system to get the flow pattern. The heat transfer module of this numerical model is developed by a special form of energy equation called Dispersion-Concentric (D-C) equation. To solve the problem, the given system was subdivided into smaller, simpler parts. This was achieved by a particular space discretization in the space dimensions, which was implemented by the construction of a mesh of the object. The Finite Element Method (FEM) formulation of a boundary value problem was used to solve these equations. For time dependent equations an implicit method, Backward differentiation formula

(BDF) was used. The work was done both for charging and discharging cycles of the heat transfer fluid through the TES tank. The predicted results were compared with the numerical results from the published literature to validate the mathematical model and the numerical scheme. Moreover, two-dimensional graphical representation of velocity, pressure, isothermal contour, streamline etc. were shown and the relation between temperature with time and space were presented. As the research work has been conducted for both single layer and multiple layers TES tank, a comparative study among the different configurations has also been represented. Temperature change with time and space, heat flux in fluids, heat flux in solids are some important key points of comparison in this work. Effect of different phase change materials on temperature were demonstrated. In the charging cycle, PCM F2 has the highest the interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) and the value is $412.3 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$ however, in the discharging cycle the value is $324.07 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$ for PCM F2. PCM F2 has also the highest value of total enthalpy difference in the charging cycle which is 1676 kJ/kg but in the discharging cycle, PCM F1 has the highest value of total enthalpy difference and the value is 1727 kJ/kg . However, this work helps to uncover a new horizon for storing thermal energy which govern us to harness more energy from sunlight by using concentrated solar collector.

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Abbreviations

TES	Thermal Energy Storage
CSP	Concentrating Solar Power / Concentrated Solar Power
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
PCM	Phase Change Material
LHTES	Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage
MLPCM	Multi-Layered Phase Change Materials
FEM	Finite Element Method
BDF	Backward Differentiation Formula
FLiNaK	LiF-NaF-KF

Subscripts

<i>f</i>	fluid
<i>s</i>	solid
<i>pc</i>	phase change
<i>ph1</i>	phase 1
<i>ph2</i>	phase 2
<i>i</i>	inner
<i>o</i>	outer

Symbols

A_{tank}	Area of the tank	m^2
A_f	Area occupied by fluid	m^2
a_{sf}	Specific surface area	m^2
C_L	Distribution of latent heat	kJ/kg
C_p	Specific heat of heat transfer fluid	$J/(kg \cdot K)$
C_{pf}	Specific heat of PCM when it is liquid	$J/(kg \cdot K)$
C_{ps}	Specific heat of PCM when it is solid	$J/(kg \cdot K)$
D_{tank}	Diameter of the tank	m
d_p	Particle diameter	m^2
E_i	Internal energy	kJ/kg
H	Height of the tank	m
H_{ref}	Reference Enthalpy	kJ/kg
H_0	Total Enthalpy	kJ/kg
h	Interstitial heat transfer coefficient	$J/(m^2 \cdot K)$
h_f	Volumetric heat transfer coefficient	$J/(m^3 \cdot K)$
h_s	True heat transfer coefficient between solid and fluid	$J/(m^2 \cdot K)$
k	Thermal conductivity of fluid	$W/(m \cdot K)$
k_s	Thermal conductivity of PCM at solid phase	$W/(m \cdot K)$
k_l	Thermal conductivity of PCM at liquid phase	$W/(m \cdot K)$
$k_{f\,eff}$	Effective thermal conductivity of fluid	$W/(m \cdot K)$
K	Specific permeability or intrinsic permeability of the medium	m^2
L	Latent heat of fusion	kJ/kg
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	kg/s
m_{in}	Mass flow entering the control volume	kg
m_{out}	Mass flow exiting the control volume	kg
m_{stored}	Mass stored inside the control volume	kg
Nu	Nusselt number	1
P	Pressure	Pa

Pr	Prandtl number	1
R	Particle radius	m
Re_p	Particle Reynolds number	1
T_f	Temperature of fluid	$^{\circ}C$
T_s	Temperature of solid	$^{\circ}C$
T_{pc}	Phase change temperature	$^{\circ}C$
u_f	Seepage velocity, filtration velocity, superficial velocity, Darcy velocity	m/s
U	Intrinsic average velocity	m/s
V	Total volume of the tank and	m^3
V_f	Volume of fluid	m^3

Greek Symbols

α_m	Mass fraction	1
ρ_f	Density of heat transfer fluid	kg/m^3
ρ_s	Density of PCM at solid phase	kg/m^3
ρ_l	Density of PCM at liquid phase	kg/m^3
μ	Viscosity of fluid	$Pa \cdot s$
ϵ	Porosity of bed	1
θ_{pi}	Volume fraction	1

Chapter 1

Introduction

In the field of renewable energy, solar power has created its position for its abundance in nature and becomes an attractive source to generate electricity. Solar energy is radiant light and heat from the sun that is harnessed using a range of ever-evolving technologies such as solar heating, photovoltaics, solar thermal energy, solar architecture, molten salt power plants and artificial photosynthesis. It is an essential source of renewable energy, and its technologies are broadly characterized as either passive solar or active solar depending on how they capture and distribute solar energy or convert it into solar power. Active solar techniques include the use of photovoltaic systems, concentrated solar power, and solar water heating to harness the energy.

A thermocline (also known as the thermal layer) is a thin but distinct layer in a large body of fluid (e. g. water, as in an ocean or lake; or air, e. g. an atmosphere) in which temperature changes more drastically with depth than it does in the layers above or below. In the ocean, the thermocline divides the upper mixed layer from the calm deep water below. Thermocline is often seen in the tank where molten salt is stored as a form of thermal energy in the concentrated solar power (CSP) plant. A thermocline thermal energy storage system is the key element of CSP power plant which is used to store hot molten salts that have been melted by the concentrated heat of the sun. The tank is filled with solid rocks which are used as filler materials and molten salts as heat transfer media. Hot and cold fluids are stored in the same tank, and they are separated for their thermal stratification [1]. To discuss about thermal energy storage, it should be known about the scenario of energy consumption throughout the world as well as in Bangladesh. Also, different ways of storing solar energy in the form of thermal energy are also discussed here.

1.1 Energy Consumption Scenario Throughout the World

1.1.1 Global Primary Energy Consumption

Figure 1.1: Global primary energy consumption, measured in terawatt-hours [2]

Figure 1.1 shows that the need for energy in the world is increasing, especially because of the technology and the growth in the world's population [3-4]. The total energy consumed in the form of coal, gas and oil, nuclear, hydro and renewable energy sources is known as primary energy. The major sources of primary energy are coal, oil and natural gas; the demand of which is increasing day by day. Traditional biomass is the most ancient form of energy. Modern biomass, renewable and nuclear energy are different forms of modern energy and the share of them in the source of primary energy is also increasing.

1.1.2 Primary Energy Consumption in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is considered one of the fastest growing economies in the Southern-Asia, with around 60% of the total population are living in rural areas [5]. Most of them use biomass as a primary source of energy for cooking purpose. Figure 1.2 shows that the major source of our primary

energy is natural gas. Besides them, the use of oil and coal is also increasing. Fossil fuels are used as primary source of energy for the purpose of electricity generation. Other forms of energy, such as renewable, nuclear and hydro power are also different sources of primary energy. About 62.9% of Bangladeshi generated electricity comes from natural gas, while 10% is from diesel, 5% comes from coal, 3% of heavy oil, and 3.3% is of renewable sources [6].

Figure 1.2: Energy consumption by sources in Bangladesh [7]

1.1.3 Primary Energy Consumption form Solar

In Bangladesh, there is a strong possibility for solar energy, with an average daily isolation of 4-6.5 kWh/m² that falls around 300 days per annum and the maximum amount of radiation are usable in the months of March-April and minimum on December-January [8]. Figure 1.3 shows the amount of primary energy consumption from solar and figure 1.4 shows the share of primary energy from solar in Bangladesh. The country has the largest off-grid solar power program in the world, which offers experiences and lessons for other countries to expand access to clean and affordable electricity. By harnessing solar power, the program enabled 20 million Bangladeshis to access electricity [9]. In Bangladesh by using solar photovoltaic panels, solar energy is being harvested as solar home system (SHS), water pumping, irrigation, street lighting, navigational

purpose etc. Solar home system (SHS), a solar power electricity generating system has become very popular since solar power development was inaugurated in rural areas of Bangladesh in 2003 by Infrastructure Development Company Limited (IDCOL), a government owned company. Share from primary energy from solar is also increasing. In 2019 more than 0.2% primary energy is consumed from solar energy.

Figure 1.3: Primary energy consumption from solar in Bangladesh [10]

Figure 1.4: Share of primary energy from solar in Bangladesh [10]

1.2 Different forms of Solar Energy Storage

Figure 1.5: Solar energy storage classification

Figure 1.5 represents different forms of storing solar energy and this energy can be stored in many ways. The primary storage system includes thermal energy storage, electrical energy storage, chemical energy storage, mechanical energy storage and electro-magnetic energy storage system. Thermal energy storage system further can be classified as sensible heat storage and latent heat storage. Sensible heat storage described that thermal energy can be stored in the change of temperatures of substances that experience a change in internal energy. Sensible heat occurred when the material released or absorbed energy as the temperature is varied [11]. The characteristics of heat storage are storage medium has high specific heat capacity, long term stability under thermal cycling, and low thermal conductivity. The key element of energy storage is the storage material. The storage medium applied in the sensible heat storage system is rock, water, concrete, brick, engine oil, ethanol [11-14]. On the other hand, in latent heat transfer storage system heat is

stored by using phase change materials. Nitrate, carbonate and fluoride salts and their mixtures are used as phase change materials (PCM) and they change their phase during heating or cooling.

1.3 Thermal Concentrator

A high light intensity will be focused onto a small area, using mirror and lens systems. As a result of this concentration, the receiver absorbs energy from concentrator and transfers it to process being driven (engine, chemical reactor, etc.). Electrical power is produced when the concentrated light is converted to heat to drive a turbine or motor engine for power generation. In general, there are four basic types of thermal concentrating solar power CSP systems: trough, tower, parabolic and Fresnel reflector.

1.3.1 CSP Trough

Figure 1.6: Parabolic trough collectors (PTCs) connected in series (photo: SEGS III, California)

A parabolic trough is a type of solar thermal collector that is straight in one dimension and curved as a parabola in the other two, lined with a polished metal mirror. The sunlight which enters the

mirror parallel to its plane of symmetry is focused along the focal line, where objects are positioned that are intended to be heated. A single-axis or a dual-axis tracking system positions the mirror to retrieve the optimal amount of sunlight (Figure 1.6). The concentration of sunlight is applied on thermally efficient receiver tubes that is positioned along the focal line of the trough. Sometimes a transparent glass tube envelops the receiver tube to reduce heat loss. A fluid like synthetic oil, molten salt or steam circulates in the tubes absorbing the sun's heat before passing through multiple heats exchange to produce steam [15]. The steam revolves around a conventional steam cycle turbine to generate electricity.

1.3.2 CSP Tower

Figure 1.7: Crescent Dunes Solar Energy Project as seen from an airliner

Employs field of mirrors called "heliostats" that individually follow the sun on two axes and reflect sunlight to a receiver at the top of a tower (Figure 1.7). Concentrated solar power (CSP, also known as concentrating solar power, concentrated solar thermal) systems generate solar power by using

mirrors or lenses to concentrate a large area of sunlight onto a receiver. Concentrated solar thermal is seen as one viable solution for renewable, pollution-free energy. Early CSP tower systems generated steam directly in the receiver. These collect the sun's heat in a heat transfer fluid that flows through the receiver. Concentration is about 600-1000 times. The temperature of the fluid (steam, air, molten salt) that circulates in the tubes is 500-800°C. In this type, with a lower required salt inventory, the operating temperature is high compared to that in CSP trough. Its disadvantage is that each mirror must have its own dual-axis control.

1.3.3 Parabolic Dish Collectors

Figure 1.8: Euro Dish Stirling parabolic dish solar collector is an example of de-centralized solar technology. Some spec: diameter 8.5 m, aperture 56.7 m², average concentration factor 2500 [16]

It is an individual unit composed of solar concentrator, a receiver and an engine or generator. Multiple mirror facets are the basis in this concentrator that effectively track the sun on two axes and reflect solar radiation towards a receiver (Figure 1.8). The latter is set up on an arm at the focal point of the reflectors and contains a motor generator combination that operates using either a sterling engine or a small gas turbine [15]. Dish system is between 10 kW and 25 kW in size compared with other CSP technologies and can be placed on a varied terrain using small quantities

of water. Even more dish conversion efficiencies are the highest reaching over 30% [15]. Its disadvantage is that the conversion from heat to electricity needs the moving of heavy engine, which requires a strong tracking system.

1.3.4 Linear Fresnel reflector

Figure 1.9: Illustration of compact linear Fresnel reflector (CLFR). (Courtesy of Department of Energy) [17]

Fresnel reflectors depend on flat or nearly flat mirror arrays to reflect sunlight onto elevated linear absorbers or receiver tubes. Water is the typical thermal that flows through the tubes and is converted into steam (Figure 1.9). Without the need for costly heat exchanger, steam can also be generated directly in the solar field. The advantage of this type is that the receiver doesn't move with the mirror as in the CSP trough, so it doesn't require rotating coupling between the receivers and the field header piping, thus providing additional design flexibility [15]. This type is cheaper than parabolic reflector, but it requires a mirror above the tube to refocus the missing rays or a multi-tube receiver that is large enough to capture missing rays without putting a mirror.

1.4 Thermal Energy Storage System

Solar thermal energy must be stored to produce electricity at night. A thermocline thermal energy storage tank consists in using one single tank to store sensible heat. At almost any time, three zones coexist in the tank: a hot fluid zone at the top, a cold fluid zone at the bottom, and an intermediate zone called thermocline. Filling the tank with solid materials enables to reduce cost and to maintain the thermal stratification during stand-by periods. The storage is used only in CSP tower and trough. There are multiple ways to store energy; the most important are:

1.4.1 Conventional Two Tank System

1.4.1.1 Two Tank Direct System

Figure 1.10: Two-tank direct storage system [18]

Figure 1.10 shows the traditional two tank direct system of thermal energy storage. Same fluid used to collect heat and store it. The fluid is stored in two different tanks: one for the high temperature and the second one for the low temperature. Fluid from the second tank launched to the receiver, its temperature becomes very high, and then it is stored in the high temperature tank to be flowed to the heat exchanger for generating steam, in order to produce electricity when needed later.

1.4.1.2 Two Tank Indirect System

Figure 1.11: Two tank indirect system [18]

Two-tank indirect systems (Figure 1.11) work in the same way as two-tank direct systems, but there are two different fluids, one for the heat's transfer and another for the storage [19]. Direct systems are more easily integrated into the plant, requiring minimum addition of piping or secondary equipment. On the contrary, indirect systems require an additional line and heat exchanger. Beyond this though, the same modelling approach can be applied to both systems by merely substituting the properties of the working fluid(s).

1.4.2 Single Tank Thermal Storage System

In this type, there is a single tank which is used to store both the hot and the cold fluid in order to reduce the cost of a direct two-tank storage system. The hot fluid is always on top in the thermocline storage, and the zone between hot and cold fluid is called "thermocline".

1.4.2.1 Single Tank Single-Media Thermocline System

The final reduction in storage tank volume is achieved when the storage tank volume equals the storage fluid volume. As shown in Figure 1.12, the storage tank is filled with cold fluid at the beginning of the operation. The thermal energy is made available in the form of hot collector fluid and then from the bottom of the storage tank the cold fluid is withdrawn and heated. Then the storage tank is filled with the hot storage fluid again. By doing it properly, the less dense hot storage fluid will "float" on top of the cold storage fluid, creating what is termed a thermocline.

However, about 10% of height in the storage tank contains mixture of the cold and hot medium. This phenomenon occurs quite commonly in many fluid systems ranging from the ocean to residential hot-water heaters. Conventional single tank systems, due to their thermal stratifications are less desirable and maintaining stratification is much simpler in solid media. But this thermal stratification behavior can be decreased by designing a new concept of mixed media single tank thermocline system.

Figure 1.12: Single tank single-media thermocline storage system [20]

1.4.2.2 Single Tank Mixed-Media Thermocline System

Figure 1.13: Mixed-media single tank thermocline system [21]

Figure 1.13 shows the mixed-media single Tank thermocline thermal energy storage system. Once the tank volume has been reduced to a minimum through the use of single tank thermocline system, the next step in reducing the capital cost of the storage system is to reduce the cost of the storage fluid as shown in Figure. Organic heat transfer oils are typically used in high-temperature solar energy systems to avoid the cost of high-pressure plumbing systems. Unfortunately, most organic heat-transfer oils are expensive. Mixed-media thermocline storage systems seek to displace expensive heat-transfer oil inventory in storage with less expensive materials such as rock and sand.

1.5 Motivation of The Present Study

Global energy demand is increasing day by day. As a result, the fossil fuel reserve is decreasing rapidly. In near future, the fossil fuel will be exhausted completely. Besides, burning of fossil fuel is increasing the concentration of carbon-dioxide and other greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. It has a great environmental impact both on human and animal life. Hence for future, concentration should be given to make less emission or emission free technology which will provide energy without any interruption or exhaustion. This may include invention of new renewable and sustainable energy technology and improvement of the existing renewable energy technologies. A further improvement of solar thermal concentrator may contribute to meet the increasing demand of energy.

However, renewable energy fluctuates and so with the increased uptake of renewable energy comes an increased need for energy storage in order to ensure the availability of clean energy when the wind is not blowing, or the sun is not delivering solar energy. The advantages of the thermal energy storage (TES) system that motivated us to work about it are given below:

1. Thermal energy storage (TES) system reduces peak demand and level demand by storing energy when there is less demand and releasing when there is high demand.
2. It reduces CO₂ emissions and costs by making sure energy is used when it is cheaper and there is more renewable energy in the mix.
3. Increase the overall energy efficiency of energy systems.

4. Thermal energy storage is also a key part of peak shaving systems, where off-peak power is used to drive heat pumps that can produce heat or cold produced by cheaper electric power and waste heat from industrial sources in order to balance energy system loads.
5. It also helps reduce global warming and pollution and requires far less land than a coal mine or oil field.
6. Energy storage can save operational costs in powering the grid, as well as save money for electricity.
7. By introducing more flexibility into the grid, energy storage can help integrate more solar, wind and distributed energy resources. It can also improve the efficiency of the grid – increasing the capacity factor of existing resources.
8. With proper insulation of the tank the thermal energy can be usefully stored for up to a week.
9. Not only can thermal energy be employed in conjunction with other renewable energy sources, but it provides backup power, energy storage, and efficient heating and cooling alternatives.

1.6 Main Objectives of The Thesis

The objectives of this research work are listed below:

- 1 To perform numerical simulations of single layered and multi-layered PCM(s) in TES tank using different heat transfer fluids.
- 2 To determine the effect of using different PCM(s) as well as different heat transfer media on temperature in TES tank.
- 3 To observe temperature distribution of different HTF and filler materials as a function of time and position.
- 4 To make a comparative study among the alternatives based on amount of heat transfer and energy efficiency.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Renewable energy sources play an important role in providing energy services in a sustainable manner and even though their share of global energy consumption is still small, the use of renewable energy has been increasing rapidly in recent years [22]. Moreover, according to the Energy Technology Perspectives 2012 [23], stronger energy government policy actions can help these technologies to overcome their economic and technical barriers and be widely used. One of the principal barriers stands on the intermittent nature of some renewable sources, such as wind or solar energy, which suppose a mismatch between the energy production and demand periods.

Thermal energy storage (TES) is identified as a technology which can help in the management and control of these systems by eliminating this mismatch or by making peak load shifting strategies [24-25]. Latent thermal energy storage systems are considered to be more energy dense, efficient and compact and have been extensively studied [26-27]. Within this context, packed bed latent heat storage systems have been a great topic of interest because of the high heat transfer area between the storage (spheres of phase change material) and the heat transfer fluid (HTF).

These packed bed TES systems have been used for several applications such as, solar thermal energy storage [28], compressed air energy storage [29], solar cooling [30], CSP plants [31], low temperature storage systems for central air conditioning [32], energy efficient buildings and waste heat recovery systems [33]. The optimization of the design and control of such TES systems are mandatory to overcome the technological and economic barriers of this technology. Within this context, numerous experimental investigations have been carried out to study the thermal characteristics of the system during freezing and melting processes. Cho and Choi [34] performed

a parametric study based on Reynolds number and inlet temperature to study the performance of paraffin in a packed bed system in comparison to a system with water as storage material, they concluded that the average heat transfer coefficient for paraffin were larger by a maximum of 40% than the one with water during both freezing and melting; moreover, they experimentally demonstrated that the melting process is affected by the natural convection occurring at the liquid fraction inside the PCM spheres. Nallusamy et al. [35] also used paraffin in a packed bed system to study the effect of porosity and HTF flow rate in the performance of the system, the authors conclude that the used packed bed phase change materials (PCM) reduce the size of the storage tank in comparison to conventional sensible storage tanks. Stratification inside the tank has been also experimentally investigated by Oró et al. [36] demonstrating that the use of latent heat storage packed bed increases the stratification during the discharge process.

2.1 General overview of the models

Different numerical methods describing the performance of a latent packed bed TES systems are available in the literature [37-38]. These numerical models can be mainly divided into two groups [39]: single phase models and two-phase models.

2.1.1 Single Phase Models

In the single-phase models, the solid and the fluid phase are considered as a unique phase, considering that the instantaneous temperature of both solid and fluid phases is the same. According to Ismail and Stuginsky [40] this model is useful in analyzing fixed beds of both high thermal conductivity and thermal capacity in comparison to the working fluid. In this case, the instantaneous temperatures of the solid and fluid phases are equal.

The use of this methodology is not popular when describing PCM packed bed systems because the assumption that the HTF and PCM are at the same instantaneous temperature is only valid when using solid particles with very high thermal conductivity. The limited thermal conductivity in the PCM is well known, being around 0.2 W/m·K in paraffin and fatty acids and around 0.6 W/m·K in salts hydrate [27, 41].

However, Nagano et al. [42] proposed a single-phase model to study the performance of an air direct heat exchanger with PCM granules. The small dimension of the particles justifies the use of this model. An experimental set-up was design to validate the model with temperature sensor at different heights inside the tank. The model considered one-dimensional flow, and even air and PCM are considered to have the same temperature at each location, only the PCM accumulative term is considered. The energy conservation equation was solved using an explicit finite difference method. The authors demonstrated with the experimental and numerical results that the amount of heat per unit time and unit area can be large during phase change in the system.

2.1.2 Two Phase Models

Regarding the two-phase models, solid and fluid phases are treated separately and the boundary between the solid-fluid interface is described by using Nusselt correlations. Three different typologies exist: the continuous solid phase model [43], the Schumann's model [44] and the concentric dispersion model [30].

2.1.2.1 The Continuous Solid Phase Model

The continuous solid phase model considers the system as a continuous porous medium and not as a medium composed of independent solids. It can include heat conduction in the axial and radial direction of both solid and fluid phases. Hence, even thermal gradients inside the particles cannot be modeled, the heat conduction in the packed bed can occur in the axial direction (one dimensional continuous solid phase models) or in axial and radial direction (two-dimensional continuous solid phase models). Even though the addition of heat transfer in the radial direction increases strongly the computational cost of the model, is the only model able to capture thermal gradients in this direction, which may gain importance in system with low mass flow rates subjected to heat losses to the environment or to system with inlet flows not well distributed.

Cheralathan et al. [45] developed and validated experimentally a one-dimensional continuous solid phase model to carry out a parametric study on the performance of a cool thermal energy storage system. The model assumes that the HTF is fully developed and the storage tank is well insulated. The thermal conductivity of the fluid and the particles are used directly, without using correlation

for effective thermal conductivities. The authors design and test an experimental set-up to validate the model. The authors studied the influence of porosity, Stephan and Stanton numbers. Similarly, Hu et al. [46] also developed an experimental set-up to validate a similar model used to optimize the design of a direct contact condenser used in a solar driven humidification-dehumidification desalination plant. Here, two-phase HTF (air and water) is considered in the model. The analysis concluded that for this application a water to air mass flow ratio around 1.5 is advised, and that the use of small high thermal conductivity particles are the ideal candidates instead of PCM.

Another one-dimensional continuous phase model was developed by Aldoss and Rahman [47] to compare the performance of a single-PCM and multi-PCM packed bed thermal energy storage systems. The authors demonstrated that using multi-PCM design provides higher performance in both charging and discharging processes. However, using more than three stages of PCM inside the packed bed do not provide significant improvements. Multiple layer packed bed system was also studied by Zanganeh et al. [48] using a one-dimensional continuous phase model. In that case, instead of multiple layers of PCM the authors proposed a novel thermal energy storage for concentrated solar thermal power based on a packed bed of rocks with a small amount of PCM at the top of the bed. The addition of the PCM stabilizes strongly the outflow temperature during discharging, eliminating temperature drop from sensible heat storage systems. Even the model does not consider thermal gradients inside the spheres, the convection heat transfer coefficient was adjusted to consider the intra-particle conduction [49].

Similarly, Wu and Fang [50] used an effective convective heat transfer coefficient in a one-dimensional phase model, where the conductive thermal resistance of the spherical shell and PCM is included in the convective term that describes the solid-fluid boundary. The authors studied the performance of a packed bed system when using myristic acid as phase change material. This model does not include natural convection of the PCM spheres; however, it considered heat losses through the tank wall. The numerical results were compared against experimental data from Nallusamy et al. [51]. In addition, the same model was used by Wu et al. [52] to evaluate the performance of n-tetradecane as PCM in a packed bed cool thermal energy storage system. In the model used in both studies, the thermal conductivity of the HTF is assumed directly to drive the conduction inside the continuous media. However, Ismail and Stuginsky [40], highlights the importance of using an effective thermal conductivity in order to consider in the model conduction

through the solid particles, conduction through the contact solid, radiation between the solid surfaces, film convection through the fluid layer involving the solid particles, and others.

In this way Rady [53] used an effective thermal conductivity in the axial direction. Here, an important innovation was provided since the model was able to evaluate the performance of multiple granular phase change components. The author distinguished the latent heat and their melted fraction of the two different materials. After an experimental validation process, the model was used into a parametric study to study the mixing ratio and Reynolds number for constant inlet charging and discharging temperatures. It was concluded that an appropriate selection of the mixing ratio will lead to a significant enhancement of the overall storage unit performance in comparison to the single granular phase change material composite. This optimum mixing ratio is independent of the value of Reynolds number. Moreover, an exergy analysis was conducted to demonstrate that the use of these systems reduces significantly the exergy destroyed.

Benmansour et al. [54] used effective thermal conductivity for the fluid both for axial and radial heat transfer. They developed a two-dimensional continuous solid phase model using air as HTF. The fluid energy equation was transformed using finite differences and solved implicitly while the solid particles was solved using fully explicit scheme. Arkar et al. [55] also uses two-dimensional continuous solid phase model to study the performance of a free cooling system based on two packed bed latent heat thermal energy storage systems. The authors justified considered an adaptation of the mathematical model because a non-uniform radial distribution of the axial fluid velocity due to small tube-to-sphere diameter ratio. The numerical model was used to predict the heat storage outlet air temperature and create Fourier series which were implemented into TRNSYS simulation program.

2.1.2.2 The Schumann's Model

the Schumann's model is a two-phase model in which heat conduction is not considered neither for the axial nor the radial direction. Hence, only convection between solid-fluid phases and heat losses to the environment are integrated in the model.

This methodology was one of the first attempts to describe numerically the behavior of packed bed thermal storage systems. Its simplicity stands in taking a lumped capacitance approach to the solid particles and assuming the convection coefficients independent of time and space. Sanderson and

Cunningham [56] used this simple model to investigate how the particle diameter affects the degree of axial dispersion as well as the pressure drop. Regin et al. [57, 58] adapted the Schumann's model to study the behavior of a packed bed latent heat thermal energy storage used for a solar water heating system.

The principal limitation of the Schumann's model is that it cannot take into account thermal diffusion inside the solid particles, hence no thermal gradients are considered in the spheres and heat conduction is not considered in the model as only convection is driving the heat transfer process. However, as it was previously stated, the PCM are characterized by their low thermal conductivity, which makes heat conduction thermal resistance to play an important role in the heat transfer during both charge or discharge processes. Therefore, some authors have adapted the Schumann's model in order to take into account the conductive thermal resistance by adding into the convective heat transfer at the solid-fluid boundary the conductive thermal resistance of the sphere.

The phase change is taken into account using the enthalpy method and even the model does not present any validation against experimental data, the authors conclude that the required period for a full solidification is much longer than the one required for a full melting of the PCM and that the charging and discharging rates are much higher if reducing the diameter of the capsules.

A similar adaption of the Schumann's model was used by Tumilowicz et al. [59] to study the performance of a thermocline with PCM packed bed storage. Here the authors used an effective convective heat transfer in the case that the size of encapsulated filler is large and gives a large Biot number [60-61]. The authors used the method of characteristics to solve the system of algebraic equations. The results were verified against analytical solutions and demonstrated that the operation of thermocline can be predicted without consuming high computational resources using the method of characteristics.

2.1.2.3 The Dispersion-Concentric model

In the concentric dispersion model, the thermal conduction inside the solid is taken into account, and two different energy equations are solved altogether, one for the solid phase and one for the fluid phase. It assumes a thermal gradient inside the solid particles and no inter-particle heat transfer; hence heat is only transferred between the fluid and the bed. This method is based on a

two-phase model and treats the packed bed as an isotropic porous medium consisting of independent spherical particles. This approach is the only that solves the thermal distribution inside the solid particles.

In the concentric dispersion models the cylindrical container is divided into elements in the axial direction in which fluid temperature is considered uniform. All the spheres at the same height are considered to behave equal. A concentric dispersion model was developed by Ismail and Henríquez [62], where the tank is divided into a number of axial layers and the fluid only exchanges heat with the particles. Moreover, the model takes into account the natural convection of the liquid phase of the PCM using an effective thermal conductivity. The model was validated using experimental data provided by the authors and is solved using a finite difference approach and moving grid technique. The working fluid entry temperature, the mass flow as well as the capsule temperature were investigated.

In the same way, Wu et al. [63] used a similar approach but with considering axial heat conduction in for the bed and the fluid. The model also uses an effective thermal conductivity to predict natural convection inside the PCM particles. However, the heat losses to the environment are not considered and the phase change is considered to occur at a unique temperature, the model was not validated against experimental data. The study concludes that the latent heat storage capacity of the PCM spheres is only about 70% of the total heat storage capacity of the system, which is due to the sensible cooling of the PCM and HTF.

Another concentric dispersion model was developed by Bédécarrats et al. [64]. Here, in order to determine the heat transfer coefficient between the solid spheres and the HTF, the ratio between Gr/Re^2 is used. In the case that this ratio is higher than the unit, free convection is considered dominant in comparison to forced convection. The numerical model was validated against experimental data [65] and was used to study the effect of the final inlet temperature and the inlet flow rate on the time for complete storage. Moreover, Galione et al. [66] incorporated the momentum equation in the heat transfer fluid to study the performance of a thermocline-PCM thermal storage concept for CSP plants. The model was validated against the experimental data from Pacheco et al. [67] and conclude that the PCM layers if located at the top and bottom of the thermocline act as a thermal buffer, forcing the outlet temperature of the tank be close to the fusion temperatures and hence inside the desired thermal range of the application. Furthermore, Galione

et al. [68] demonstrated that the use of multilayered solid-PCM prevents thermocline degradation, increasing the efficiency in the use of the overall thermal capacity of the system, and requires less amount of encapsulated PCM than a cascaded PCM concept to store almost the same energy. The same system was analyzed economically by Zhao et al. [69] concluding that multi-layered solid-PCM thermocline concept with an optimum configuration is more cost-competitive than any other thermocline TES system on the same design requirements and operating conditions.

Yang et al. [70] modeled a storage packed bed tank with PCM having different melting points. The model, based on concentric dispersion method, presents one dimensional assumption and includes the natural convection inside the spheres by using an effective thermal conductivity. Moreover, heat conduction of the HTF in the axial direction is considered using another correlation that modifies the thermal conductivity of the HTF. The numerical solution was based on control volume integration method using a fully implicit time integration scheme. The results were validated against experimental measurements [51] and are used to demonstrate that the system with PCM multiple-type packed bed melts faster than the single-type one. It was also highlighted that during the melting process the multiple-type presents higher energy transfer efficiency.

A similar model was developed by Ereǵ and Dincer [71] to test a newly developed correlation to determine the heat transfer coefficient between the PCM particles and the HTF. The authors claimed that in the correlations of the literature, the heat transfer coefficient is considered constant as the flow is assumed hydrodynamically and thermally developed. However, experimental results indicated that the coefficient varies greatly during downstream and highly affects the heat transfer taking place during the process. A set of CFD simulations was carried out to perform the new Nusselt correlation, which was validated against experimental data from Eames and Adref [72].

Molten salts are used as a HTF in the packed bed latent heat thermal energy storage system analyzed by Peng et al. [73]. The authors developed a numerical model based on the concentric dispersion methodology and use non-dimensional parameters to solve and generalize the model and the corresponding results. A mesh independent study was carried out to prove that the numerical model is consistent with 2500 elements. The numerical model is validated against experimental data from Izquierdo-Barrientos et al. [74] with average deviations of 5%. The study concludes that the particle size is a dominant parameter in the heat transfer between the HTF and the PCM. Smaller the particle diameter, the HTF temperature starts to increase later and the

effective charge time is shortened, thus increases the charge efficiency. It was also demonstrated that the increase of the inlet velocity results in a decrease of charge efficiency, as well as the use of higher thermal storage tank provides higher charge efficiency.

Furthermore, Bindra et al. [75] carried out an exergy calculation for packed bed using an experimentally validated numerical model which takes into account heat losses to the environment, thermal gradient inside the spheres and axial heat transfer in the HTF and the PCM. The parametric study carried out in the paper showed that in the case of high storage temperatures, in order to obtain higher exergy recovery with PCM storage systems, these should have lower latent heat or lower energy density, since in the case of sensible heat storage system even at high energy density, higher exergy recovery can be obtained. PCM is particularly useful if the heat is needed at a temperature near the phase change.

Karthikeyan et al. [76] used a concentric dispersion model to describe a solar system with air as HTF. The model used the enthalpy method to model the phase change. In this paper different parameters were studied in order to increase the heat transfer rate in both charging and discharging processes. It was demonstrated that in this case study the thermal conductivity of the PCM is not as critical as the low convective term because of the use of air as HTF. However, the model was used to demonstrate and quantify the effect of the PCM sphere size, the inlet HTF temperature and the effect of the mass flow rate of the HTF.

Concentric dispersion model has been also used to test the dynamic behaviour for charging/discharging processes of the molten salt packed bed TES system filled with high-temperature PCM capsules. Wu et al. [77] compared numerically the performance of non-cascaded against 3 and 5 cascaded phase change temperature systems, showing that the non-cascaded suffer from the low charging ratio requiring long charging time.

Finally, Kousksou and Bruel [78] used this methodology to test a packed bed storage system when various complex input temperature signals are considered. The system is altered significantly when some randomness is introduced at the inlet, explaining why in some cases, the PCM systems in real applications do not prove the same performance as priori expected.

2.2 Thermal Energy Storage System

2.2.1 Sensible Heat Storage System

Sensible heat storage is the simplest heat storage system. It stores the energy in sensible heat, which can be reflected by the temperature. The fluid storage media include water and oil. The solid storage media include the building fabric, metal, and rock. Take water as an example: it has heat capacity of approximately 4.2 kJ/ (kg. K) and a density of approximately 1000 kg/m³, which result in an energy density of approximately 11.7 kWh/m³ for a 10°C temperature change [79].

Tesfay and Venkatesan [1] investigate to design a TES which can produce 1MWe. In their work simulation was performed to analyze the Liquid medium STES using C. They also investigated different liquid medium TESs and out of all they selected mixed-media single-tank thermocline TES which was based on the Schumann equation. They designed and sized for low cost of manufacturing and maintenance to the minimum possible volume.

Lui et al. [80] analyzed transient characteristics of the molten salt FLiNaK (46.5%LiF-11.5%NaF-42%KF) for the TES tank compared the results with HITEC (7%NaNO₃-49%NaNO₂-44%KNO₃) salt. The main objective of their work was to analyze the transient behavior of the available molten salt FLiNaK used as the HTF in heat transfer and heat storage in a thermocline thermal energy storage (TES) system. They also analyzed thermal characteristics including temperature profiles influenced by different inlet velocities of HTF and different void fractions of porous heat storage medium.

Modi and Pérez-Segarraba [81] presented one-dimensional transient mathematical model for a single-tank thermocline thermal energy storage system. The model used temperature dependent correlations to obtain the thermophysical properties for the heat transfer fluid and considered heat loss through the tank wall. They investigated the effect of variation in important system parameters like the type of heat transfer fluid, the storage temperature difference and the cycle cut-off criterion on system performance. They also observed that the cycle durations and the time required to attain cyclic conditions are highly sensitive to not only the storage temperature difference, but also the cut-off temperature difference.

2.2.2 Latent Heat Storage System

Latent Heat Storage (LHS) is associated with a phase transition, the general term for the associated media is Phase-Change Material (PCM). During these transitions, heat can be added or extracted without affecting the material's temperature, giving it an advantage over sensible heat storage (SHS) technologies. Storage capacities are often higher as well. There are a multitude of PCMs available, including but not limited to salts, polymers, gels, paraffin waxes and metal alloys, each with different properties. This allows for a more target-oriented system design.

As the process is isothermal at the PCM's melting point, the material can be picked to have the desired temperature range. Desirable qualities include high latent heat and thermal conductivity. Furthermore, the storage unit can be more compact if volume changes during the phase transition are small. The research about PCM is popular because of this. The phase changing temperature is steady when the system is built. Different PCMs are needed for different energy storage temperatures [79].

Kalidasan et al. [82] made an attempt to consolidate the global trends and practices that had been underwent incorporating phase change materials (PCMs) in solar thermal systems in their review article. Application of phase change materials for low, medium and high temperature solar thermal systems were comprehensively reviewed and discussed in their article. They also presented the environmental benefits in terms decline in CO₂ emission, due to the use of STS in day-today life and the economic analysis of PCM based STS in terms of cost and payback period.

Ahmed et al. [83] formulated a comprehensive unsteady numerical model based on two phase Schumann model equations to evaluate performance of each proposed prototypes. They performed the numerical simulations to investigate the effect of combined sensible rod structure and multi-layered PCMs designs on thermocline temperature profiles, exergy outputs, total thermal energy storage, efficiency in the use of total storage capacity, utilization ratio and the proportion of PCM effectively changing phase. They made a comparative analysis for four different configurations, i.e., single layered sensible rod with PCM (SLSPCM) arrangement and the three cascaded layered sensible rod with PCM (CLSPCM) arrangements. The analysis presented in their study shows that the use of multi-stage PCMs having suitable combination of layer thickness and fusion temperature offer an efficient and cost-effective TES alternative.

2.2.3 Multi-Layer Thermal Energy Storage System

If a tank is consisted by such a way that different phase change materials are used in different layers thus this system is called multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) thermal energy storage system. It is a special type of latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) system where multiple layers of PCM's exists in a single tank.

The present study focuses on single layer and multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCM) thermal energy storage systems which are analyzed for different heat transfer fluids (HTF) and different phase change materials (PCM).

Elfeky et al. [84] presented two parametric studies (inverse Stefan number and dimensionless temperature difference) to optimize the values of latent heat and melting temperature of multi-layered phase change materials (MLPCM(s)) in thermocline tank for concentrating solar power (CSP) plants. They used spherical capsules filled with PCM (s) of different thermo-physical properties to fill the bed region, and the molten salt is used as heat transfer fluid (HTF). They developed the numerical model by using the Dispersion-Concentric (D-C) equations and solved the equations by MATLAB and validated against the experimental results.

Abdulla & Reddy [85] made a comparative study of single and multi-layered packed-bed thermal energy storage systems for CSP plants where the Multi-layered thermal energy storage (TES) tank consisted of three regions. Top and bottom part was packed with suitable phase change materials (PCM) and low-cost pebbles were placed in the middle region, whereas entire tank portion was filled by solid fillers in Single-layered tank system.

Galione et al. [86] proposed a concept that consists of a storage tank filled with a combination of solid material and encapsulated PCMs, forming a multi-layered packed bed, with molten salt as the heat transfer fluid. They tested virtually the performance evaluation of each of the prototypes proposed by means of a detailed numerical methodology which considered the heat transfer and fluid dynamics phenomena present in these devices. They compared the efficiencies of the storing process for the different thermocline, single PCM, cascaded PCM and the proposed multi-layered solid-PCM (MLSPCM) configurations.

Another technique called enthalpy-porosity method, which is applied to the modelling of the melting process of any pure substance. In this method, techniques for numerically modelling solid–liquid phase transitions at the continuum level have generally been divided into transformed-grid and fixed-grid approaches instead of the involvement of the moving boundary problem as numerical simulations of melting and solidification processes are critical to develop understanding of phase transformations that occur in various technologies such as additive manufacturing, thermal energy storage, anti-icing, and materials processing. Different numerical techniques have been developed to resolve the transport phenomena and the solid–liquid phase transition at different scales, which have been reviewed in different literatures [87-90]. This method is useful to determine the mass fraction of any melting materials and the mushy zone (a mixed solid–liquid region during dendritic growth) can be demonstrated with the help of 2D graph.

However, in the present study, a dispersion-concentric model is used to solve the given problem. In this method, the porous medium is considered to be built with distinct, isotropic spherical materials which is distributed uniformly. Latent heat packed bed system can be modelled by this technique. This method is useful where porous medium is involved with phase change materials. Here, the overall heat transfer scenario is important here rather melting of a single spherical particle. So, dispersion-concentric model is appropriate to solve the porous TES tank problems.

Chapter 3

Problem Formulation

3.1 Physical Model Description

A Thermocline thermal energy storage tank is an inherent part of the concentrated solar power (CSP) plant. Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2 are the detailed representation of the CSP plant loop and TES tank respectively. The main loop fluid in a CSP plant is molten salt, which is melted using concentrated solar power to reach the required high temperature. During daytime molten salt directly goes to the heat exchanger where steam is produced as well as fills the energy storage tank. The process is called the charging process.

Figure 3.1: Schematic Layout of CSP power plant

However, when sunlight is not available at night, the stored molten salt in the storage tank is used to create steam, which is then used to generate electricity. This is known as discharging process. Another cycle in the secondary loop is also active simultaneously where steam is the working fluid. Steam produced in the heat exchanger is superheated in the steam superheater section and expands in the turbine. Then the steam is condensed in the condenser where a feed pump pumps the condensate to the steam generator.

Figure 3.2: Schematic diagram of three-layer storage tank

In thermocline storage tank heat transfer fluid enters through inlet section and exits through outlet section. In the distributor region, molten salt is distributed to make the flow uniform. The velocity of the molten salt is too low to maintain the thermocline in the thermal energy storage (TES) tank. In this study multi-layered TES tank of different phase change materials is used. Three different phase change materials (PCMs) were analyzed by filling the whole tank and showing how temperature changes along with the bed height. The authors also focused their concentration on finding the temperature distribution along with the bed height by filling the tank with three different layers of PCMs. The bottom layer of the PCM is layer 1, the upper layer is layer 2 and the upmost layer is layer 3. Figure 3.3 shows the 2D geometry of the whole TES tank where figure 3.4 shows the geometry where simulation is performed for symmetry.

Figure 3.3: 2D geometry of the whole TES tank

Figure 3.4: The geometry in where simulation is run for symmetry

In this study, the tank wall is considered as fully insulated i.e., no heat can pass through the tank wall. The physical model used in the study has 1 m in height and 1 m in diameter. The diameter of the spherical encapsulated PCM particles is 0.01905 m. The bed porosity of the tank is 0.22 that means its empty volume is 22% of its total volume. It is considered that the PCMs are encapsulated in a spherical shell whose thermal conductivity is sufficiently high for uninterrupted flow of heat.

3.2 Heat Transfer Fluids and Phase Change Materials

In this research, three different heat transfer fluids have been used. Molten salt is used as heat transfer fluid (HTF). The following molten salts were used HTF. The phase change materials (PCM) are selected in such a way that their melting point is between the melting point and boiling point of HTF. Heat transfer fluids as well as phase change materials are the mixtures of different nitrate, fluoride, chloride, and carbonate salts. Here is the list of HTF and PCMs that were used in the present study [91]:

- i. Hitec Salt (7wt%NaNO₃-40wt%NaNO₂ -53wt%KNO₃)
- ii. Solar Salt (60% NaNO₃ & 40% KNO₃)
- iii. FLiNaK salt (29wt% LiF-12wt%NaF-59wt%KF)

For Hitec salt we have used the following three phase change materials (PCMs)

- i. PCM H1: Li₂CO₃-Na₂CO₃-K₂CO₃ [92-94]
- ii. PCM H2: 59.98 wt% MgCl₂ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% NaCl [84]
- iii. PCM H3: 55 wt% MgCl₂ – 45%NaCl [84]

For Solar salt we have used the following three phase change materials (PCMs)

- i. PCM S1: 59.98 wt% MgCl₂ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% NaCl [84]
- ii. PCM S2: 55 wt% MgCl₂ – 45%NaCl [84]
- iii. PCM S3: 35 wt%Li₂CO₃ – 65 wt%K₂CO₃ [95]

For FLiNaK salt we have used the following three phase change materials (PCMs)

- i. PCM F1: 35 wt%Li₂CO₃ – 65 wt%K₂CO₃ [84]
- ii. PCM F2: 22 wt%Li₂CO₃-16 wt%Na₂CO₃-62 wt%K₂CO₃ [84, 96-97]
- iii. PCM F3: 51wt% K₂CO₃ and 49 wt%Na₂CO₃ [97, 98]

3.3 Properties of Heat Transfer Fluid

Molten salt is used as a primary coolant within a nuclear reactor or heat transport medium from the Very High Temperature Reactor (VHTR) to a processing plant; for example, a hydrogen-production plant. Several fluids are under consideration for heat transfer fluids between the Very High Temperature Reactor (VHTR), such as the Next Generation Nuclear Plant (NGNP), and the downstream processes. Prominent among the candidate fluids are helium gas and molten salts. Applicability of molten salts as heat transferring coolants has been assessed by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) researchers: Williams [99] and Williams et al. [100]. Williams [99] contended that the coolants must have the following characteristics:

Chemical stability at high temperatures (500–800°C).

Radiolytic stability in a high radiation environment (for primary coolant only).

Freezing (melting) temperature as low as possible, preferably lower than 525°C.

Large specific heat and thermal conductivity.

Low vapor pressures that are substantially less than one atmosphere at operating temperatures and are thus not volatile.

Compatible with high-temperature materials, alloys, graphite, and ceramics.

Molten salts appear to be excellent candidates that meet most of these requirements. However, no single component salt meets the requirement of low melting temperature; multi-component eutectic mixtures are needed to meet the melting temperature requirement. Some multi-component eutectic salt mixtures have melting temperatures less than 500°C. The use of eutectic mixtures ensures compositional and phase stability, and therefore, uniform thermophysical properties in the operating temperature range [101- 102].

3.3.1 Properties of Hitec salt

Sodium Nitrate-Sodium Nitrite-Potassium Nitrate ($\text{NaNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2\text{-KNO}_3$)

Sodium nitrate-sodium nitrite-potassium nitrate ($\text{NaNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2\text{-KNO}_3$) mixture may have composition in the range of (7-49-44 mol%, 7-40-53 wt.%) [91]. Melting point of commercial Hitec salt is 142 °C [103-104] and its thermal stability is 530 °C under an inert gas atmosphere [105]. It was utilized in THEMIS solar power plant during 1980s [106,107].

Density:

Several studies can be mentioned, with very little differences among their mathematical expression and nearly the same after calculating values, e.g., Chang et al. [108], Janz and Tomkins [109], Yang and Garimella [110], Wu et al. [111], Boerema et al. [103] and Serrano-López et al. [112].

Viscosity:

Different correlations have been published for the Hitec[®] mixtures. Gaune [113] used a second order function of temperature for the range of 473-773 K. Janz and Tomkins [109] reported a third order polynomial correlation, but it shows an excessive slope at high temperatures regarding the others. This probably happens due to thermal decomposition of nitrates. Recently, other authors have used other expressions, e.g., Yang and Garimella [110], Boerema et al. [103], Siegel et al. [114], Chen et al. [115] and Wu et al. [111] have correlated to a linear expression for the viscosity of Hitec salt. Yang and Garimella [110] gave an exponential correlation for this salt which is also suggested by Serrano-López et al. [112] for the temperature range $T \in 525\text{-}773$.

Boerema et al. [103] gives the higher viscosity of all the correlations at low temperatures, as well as Wu et al. gives the lowest one, and shows a crescent function of temperature. The expression provided by Yang and Garimella is selected as the most representative.

Janz et al. [109] gave a correlation for viscosity as a function of temperature in the temperature range of 420-710 K with an uncertainty of $\pm 16\%$:

Specific Heat Capacity, C_p :

Correlations for the commercial Hitec[®] have been reported by Janz and Tomkins [109], Hoffman and Cohen [116] and Boerema et al. [103], using different expressions. Constant values were reported by Wu et al. [111] and Yang and Garimella [110], and this latter gives the same number

as found in the SAM database. The computed standard deviation is 473.23 when using all reviewed data. A value of $C_p = 1560 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ is suggested by Serrano-López et al. [112] due to the agreement of recent proposals with early measurements, giving a 2.45 % of deviation from average. The specific heat capacity of Hitec is 1.55 J/ (g. K) at 170–510 °C reported by Janz and Truong [107], whereas almost near values of 1.56 J/ (g. K) at 300 °C [117, 118] and 1.57 J/ (g. K) [119] were also reported in the literature. Likewise, some lower values had also been reported accounting for 1.37, 1.36 and 1.48 J/ (g. K) at 200, 275 and 350 °C, respectively [120]. Janz et al. [109] gave a correlation for specific heat capacity in terms of temperature for the temperature range of 426–776 K with an uncertainty of $\pm 5\%$.

Thermal Conductivity, k :

Serrano-López et al. [112] had accessed SAM database, in order to compare values with Janz and Tomkins [109], Yang and Garimella [110], Wu et al. [111], Cooke et al. [121], Tufeu et al. [122], Omotani and Nagashima [123], Santini et al. [124] and Boerema et al. [103]. The global standard deviation for this property and salt had been computed about 0.097. Although there is a general disagreement among most recent reports, Serrano-López et al. [112] suggested a value of $k = 0.48 \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m.K}} \right)$ which is also in coherence with DiGuilio and Teja [125] arguments for KNO_3 and nitrate mixtures. The deviation from average for this last value is calculated to be around 4.36 %.

In this research work, we used the following correlation for the thermophysical properties of Hitec salt.

Density [112],

$$\rho \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = 2279.799 - 0.7324 T (K) \quad (3.1)$$

Viscosity [112],

$$\mu (Pa.s) = \exp(-4.343 - 2.0143 ((\ln(T(K) - 273) - 5.0011))) \quad (3.2)$$

Specific heat capacity [112],

$$C_p \left(\frac{J}{kg.K} \right) = 1560 \quad (3.3)$$

Thermal conductivity [112],

$$k \left(\frac{W}{m.K} \right) = 0.48 \quad (3.4)$$

3.3.2 Properties of Solar salt

Solar Salt has widely been examined as the most mature molten nitrate salt solution. It is a binary salt mixture of KNO_3 - $NaNO_3$ (40–60 wt %) and has extensively been used in commercial molten-salt CSP systems [126]. It melts at 220 °C and has the thermal stability of 600 °C [127,128].

Density:

Parameters for the so-called Solar Salt (also known as draw salt) have been either published for the equimolar composition (near 1:1 molar ratio), and for the cheaper commercial mixture (0.64-0.36), or 60-40 wt%. However, there are no significant differences in terms of density. This useful mixture was reported by Janz et al. [129] giving a second order equation in terms of temperature, and which allows to take into account the molar percentage of KNO_3 .

Its density tends to decrease linearly as the temperature increases [130]. Zavoico [131] concisely expressed a correlation for density of Solar salt which is valid from 260 °C to 593 °C.

The eutectic composition of this salt was also studied by James and Liu [132], Carling et al. [133] and Nissen [134]. Carling et al. [133] reported two correlations, considering the thermal decomposition of nitrate to nitrite at extended time experiments. Nissen [134] gives a time dependent expression which is suggested by Serrano-López et al. [112].

Xu et al. [135] also used a correlation for the thermal conductivity of solar salt which was referred by Zavoico [131] within a temperature range of 300 °C - 600 °C.

Viscosity:

For the binary Solar Salt, negligible differences were found for viscosity between equimolar and commercial compositions. Initial measurements made by Murgulescu and Zuca were reported by

Janz et al. [129] for the range $T \in (525 - 725)$ after a critical review. These correlations included the 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 mol% of NaNO_3 , with Arrhenius form for the two first and a third order polynomial for the others. New Arrhenius expressions were reported by Janz [136] for the same molar composition cases, revising again the measurements mentioned above. For the equimolar salt, experimental data was given by Nissen [134], making a polynomial correlation for the whole range $T \in [573 - 873]$ K and giving a 2.33 % of deviation from the average values used lately by Zavoico [131] for the Basis Document of the Solar Power Tower. In any case, the effect of molar composition is almost negligible.

From the correlation of Nissen [134] it is found that the viscosity of Solar Salt to be around 1.03 mPa s at 600 °C and Pacheco et al. [130] represented the viscosity data as third order function of temperature.

However, in a recent study, different values have also been reported, i.e., 3.42 mPa s at 500 °C [137] and 2.66 ± 0.17 mPa s at 500 °C [138].

Specific Heat Capacity, C_p :

Specific heat capacity of Solar Salt was reported as linearly dependent on temperature [124] and Bauer et al. [126] reported the value of 1.54 ± 0.077 J/ (g. K) at ~250–520 °C. Moreover, a similar value of 1.52 J/ (g. K) has been observed at 450 °C [139]. There is some discrepancy about the specific heat capacity describing a lower value of 1.44 J/ (g. K) at 275–375 °C [140] and a higher value of 1.64 J/ (g. K) at 400 °C [141]. An inconsistent value was also reported in the literature where theoretical calculation based on conventional models had quantified a lower value of 1.34 J/ (g. K) at 300–500 °C [138].

Where, Zavoico [131] referred the specific heat capacity formulas for solar salt as a function of temperature between 300 to 600°C (570 to 11 110°F). Elfeky et al. [84] and Xu et al. [135] used the same correlation, however the only difference is they used negative sign before temperature variable term.

Serrano-López et al. [112] suggested that the actualized values offered by SAM may be a good choice with a 2.36 % of deviation from the global average.

Thermal Conductivity, k:

The scattering of data is even larger for nitrate compositions, as they have been studied extensively. Thermal decomposition of this kind of salts must be taken also into account, which can be significantly enhanced by controlling the atmosphere, as recently discussed by Olivares [142]. Several reports for Solar Salt (with different molar compositions) had been reviewed, and also the SAM data had been correlated by linear regression: Janz et al. [109], McDonald and H. Ted Davis [143], Omotani et al. [144], Tufeu et al. [122] and Zavoico [131]. According to DiGuilio and Teja [125], temperature dependence must show negative slope. In general, correlated values give a maximum of 0.58 and a minimum of 0.42 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for the range $T \in [600 - 730]$. Serrano-López et al. [112] suggested a constant $k = 0.45 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ which is found to be a good choice, showing a 10.12 % of deviation from average.

Bauer et al. [126] described the thermal conductivity of Solar Salt about $k = 0.5 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ at $\sim 250\text{--}500$ °C within estimated error of 15%. Adding to that, a similar value of $k = 0.58 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ was reported at 500 °C [145]. Elfeky et al. [84] and Xu et al. [135] used the same correlation for the thermal conductivity of solar salt which was referred by Zavoico [131].

In this research work, we used the following correlation for the thermophysical properties of Solar salt.

Density [131],

$$\rho \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = 2090 - 0.636 T \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.5)$$

Viscosity [130],

$$\mu \text{ (Pa}\cdot\text{s)} = 22.71 - 0.12 T \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} + 2.28 \times 10^{-4} T^2 \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} - 1.47 \times 10^{-7} T^3 \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.6)$$

Specific heat capacity [131],

$$C_p \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}} \right) = 1443 + 0.172 T \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.7)$$

Thermal conductivity [131],

$$k \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}} \right) = 0.443 + 1.9 \times 10^{-4} T \text{ (}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.8)$$

3.3.3 Properties of FLiNaK salt

Lithium Fluoride - Sodium Fluoride - Potassium Fluoride (LiF- NaF- KF)

FLiNaK salt is a eutectic mixture of 46.5%LiF, 11.5%NaF, and 42% KF by mole and 29% LiF, 12% NaF and 59% KF by weight. Molten fluoride salts are also worthwhile for HTF and TES applications owing to thermal stability up to 700 °C. However, fluoride salts are toxic, costly in operation (~2.4 US \$/kg) and possess higher melting point (~450 °C) [146,147]. Fluorides are intrinsically corrosive, specifically at higher temperature, thereby dissolving the protective oxide film which in turn showed chemical instability and conversion to metal fluorides, consequently. The presence of impurities may cause severe corrosion rates of materials [148,149]. Mostly considered salt with composition of KF-LiF-NaF (59-29-12 wt %) is relatively stable and nontoxic fluoride salt [150]. It has melting point of 454 °C and stability limit of >700 °C [151].

Density, ρ :

The density of eutectic FLiNaK has been experimentally measured and estimated in different occasions, as reported by Grimes et al. [152], Janz and Tomkins [109], Chrenková et al. [153], Cibulkova et al. [154] and Salanne et al. [155] for several temperature ranges. Williams et al. [100], Ambrosek et al. [156], and Korkut and Hançerlioğulları [157] used Grimes et al. [152] as a reference. Sohal et al. referred some correlations of density as a function of temperature in their research work from different references [158-161].

which has an uncertainty of $\pm 2\%$ and is valid only in the temperature range of 940–1170 K. The last correlation was also suggested by Serrano-López et al. [112] of density for FLiNaK salt for the temperature range of $T \in 933 - 1170$ with a standard deviation of 0.38% which is also reported in the literature of Chrenková et al. [153].

Viscosity, μ :

Cohen and Jones [162] offered measurements for FLiNaK viscosity, later reported by Grimes et al. [152], Powers et al. [163], Korkut and Hançerlioğulları [157]. Vriesema [160] used a different data and these values have been correlated using the same density of his heat transfer experiments. More recently, results provided by Chrenková et al. [153] and correlation listed by Janz and Tomkins [109] give nearly the same numbers and both of them can be over-ranged by the equation of Cibulková et al. [154] up to 1163 K. After a comparison, and taking into account the discussed

argument for FLiNaK density, Serrano-López et al. [112] suggested the correlation of Chrenková et al. [153] for the range $T \in [773 - 1163]$ K. However, they found 9.87 % deviation from the average raises to due to the closeness of all values.

Specific Heat Capacity, C_p :

Proposals were made by Janz and Tomkins [98], Kato et al. [164] and Salanne et al. [155]. Kato et al. [164] values are based on thermal diffusivity data. Vriesema [160] used a constant value of $1890 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$. Rogers et al. [165] also reported a correlation for this property with positive slope. Published data are higher than ideal behavior in agreement with Beneš and Konings [166]. After verifying the strong correlation among the constant reported data (standard deviation of 208.46), a heat capacity of $C_p = 1880 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ is suggested by Serrano-López et al. [112] to be a good value with 6.07 % of deviation from average.

Williams et al. [100] measured a value of $1884.06 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ at 973 K, which has an accuracy of $\pm 10\%$. The above Equation gives a specific heat capacity value of $2011.47 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ at 973 K, which is $\sim 6.7\%$ off from the measured value of Williams et al. [100]. Grele and Gedeon [158] gave a value of $2090 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$.

Thermal Conductivity, k :

FLiNaK investigations show a wide range of data from 0.6 to $4.5 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$. Vriesema [160] gave a value of $1.3 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$, whereas Grele and Gedeon [158], and Hoffman and Lones [159] gave a value of $4.5 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$. Williams et al. [100] indicated that the thermal conductivity at 973 K will be in the range $0.6\text{--}1.0 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ and this correlation is applicable in the temperature range of $790\text{--}1080 \text{ K}$. Smirnov et al. [167] have suggested a correction of ± 0.012 for the thermal conductivity values, which may give an uncertainty of 1-5%, depending on the absolute value of thermal conductivity.

Kato et al. [164] values are derived from thermal diffusivity data. Ewing et al. [168] showed decreasing transmission coefficients, which was explained due to solution of container components. For the usual composition Beneš and Konings [166] conclusions recommended a linear equation with positive slope. However, DiGuilio and Teja [125] discussed this behavior for the alkali halides (descent slope). The standard deviation is too high if values of Grele and Gedeon

[158], Hoffman and Lones [159], Grimes et al. [152], Powers et al. [163] and Janz and Tomkins [109] are used in calculations, growing up to 1.29; but it decreases till 0.21 when these anomalous values are ignored. Serrano-López et al. [112] suggested a constant value $0.85 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ for thermal conductivity of FLiNaK salt in agreement with Kato et al. [150] and Smirnov et al. [152]. In this research work, we used the following correlation for the thermophysical properties of FLiNaK salt.

Density [109],

$$\rho \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = 2579.3 - 0.624 T(K) \quad (3.9)$$

Viscosity [112, 153],

$$\mu(\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}) = 0.0000249 \times 10^{\left(\frac{1944}{T(K)} \right)} \quad (3.10)$$

Specific heat capacity [112],

$$C_p \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{K}} \right) = 1880 \quad (3.11)$$

Thermal conductivity [112],

$$k \left(\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m} \cdot \text{K}} \right) = 0.85 \quad (3.12)$$

3.4 Properties of Phase Change Materials

Successful utilization of the latent heat storage unit (LHSU) depends considerably on the selection of the phase change materials (PCM), which plays an important role in development of LHSU. The feasibility of using a particular PCM for an LHSU is based on some desirable thermo-physical, kinetic, and chemical properties of the PCM. These desirable thermal, physical, kinetic, chemical and economical properties of PCM are listed below in Table 1.

Table 3.1 Desirable properties of phase change energy storage materials [169,170].

Properties	Desirable characteristics
Thermal properties	<p>Suitable melting point for particular application</p> <p>High latent heat of fusion per unit volume</p> <p>High thermal conductivity of solid and liquid phases for better heat transfer</p> <p>Higher specific heat for additional sensible heat storage</p> <p>Little or no subcooling during freezing</p>
Physical properties	<p>Favorable phase equilibrium</p> <p>High density for smaller container volume</p> <p>Small volume change during phase transition</p> <p>Low vapor pressure to reduce the containment problem</p> <p>Reproducibility in the congruent during entire thermal cycle</p>
Chemical properties	<p>Long term chemical stability with no chemical decomposition,</p> <p>Non-toxic,</p> <p>Non-explosive mixture,</p> <p>Low corrosion potential and compatible with materials of construction</p>

Economic properties	Available in plenty Inexpensive Ease recycling and treatment
Mechanical	High fracture toughness, Compressive strength
Environmental	Low manufacturing energy requirement and CO ₂ footprint

3.4.1 Classifications of Phase Change Materials

Wide varieties of phase change materials are available based on a range of temperature required. PCMs are generally classified into three types: Organic, Inorganic and Eutectics [171-174] as shown in the Figure.

Figure 3.5: Classification of phase change materials

3.4.1.1 Organic PCM

Organic materials are generally categorized into paraffins and non-paraffins. Usually, this type of materials melts and solidifies congruently, i.e., under repeated melting or solidification cycles, there is no phase segregation. Organic PCMs presents self-nucleation, which is the property of crystallizing with little or no super cooling, and they are not corrosive in nature. Paraffin is further distinguished into paraffin hydrocarbons and paraffin waxes.

Paraffins: These are mostly straight chain alkanes. Their melting point and latent heat increase with increase in chain length. Availability in large temperature range, congruent melting and good nucleating properties, reliable and predictable behavior, safe and non- corrosive, economic – are the main advantages of paraffins. The main disadvantages are low thermal conductivity, non-compatibility with plastic containers and Moderately flammable.

Non-paraffins: These are most numerous PCMs with varied properties. Most of them are esters, fatty acids, alcohols and glycols with high heat of fusion. The main advantages of non-paraffins are high heat of fusion, inflammability. Low thermal conductivity, low flashpoint, instability at higher temperature, High cost are the disadvantages of non-paraffins PCM.

3.4.1.2 Inorganic PCM

Inorganic materials are generally salt hydrates; they are typically an alloy of inorganic salts and water forming a crystalline solid of general formula $A.B. nH_2O$.

Salt hydrates: These are nothing but the alloys of inorganic salt and water, in which crystalline solids are formed. Solid-liquid phase transition of salt hydrates is the process of hydration and dehydration. High latent heat of fusion per unit volume, relatively high thermal conductivity, small volume changes on melting, inexpensiveness are the major advantages of salt hydrates. The main disadvantages of slat hydrates are phase separation, poor nucleation properties and incongruent melting.

Metallics: These are the low melting metals and metal eutectics. High thermal conductivity, high heat of fusion per unit volume, low vapor pressure are the main advantages and higher weight is the main disadvantage of metallic compounds.

3.4.1.3 Eutectics

A eutectic is a material composed of two or more components. They solidify congruently and without segregation at a temperature that is normally lower than the one at which single components solidifies, called “eutectic temperature”. Their thermal application is relatively new hence, a limited amount of information is known. They usually have sharp melting points comparable to pure substances and a higher volumetric storage density than organic compounds. The phase change materials (PCM) are selected such a way that their melting points should be between the melting point and boiling point of heat transfer fluids (HTF).

3.4.2 PCMs for Hitec Salt

Table 3.2 Thermo-physical properties of the multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) for Hitec salt:

Arrangement	PCM H1 [92-94]	PCM H2 [84]	PCM H3 [84]
Melting temperature (°C)	307	382.1	439.8
Latent heat of fusion (kJ·kg ⁻¹)	177	197.6	214.9
Solid density (kg·m ⁻³)	2250	2118	2109
Solid thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	0.5	1.0	1.0
Liquid thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	0.5	1.0	1.0
Solid specific heat capacity (J·kg ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	1223	928	1005
Liquid specific heat capacity (J·kg ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	1665	1035	1096

Where,

PCM H1: Li₂CO₃-Na₂CO₃-K₂CO₃

PCM H2: 59.98 wt% MgCl₂ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% NaCl.

PCM H3: 55 wt% MgCl₂ – 45%NaCl.

3.4.3 PCMs for Solar Salt

Table 3.3 Thermo-physical properties of the multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) for Solar salt [84, 95]:

Arrangement	PCM S1	PCM S2	PCM S3
Melting temperature (°C)	382.1	439.8	505
Latent heat of fusion (kJ·kg ⁻¹)	197.6	214.9	344
Solid density (kg·m ⁻³)	2118	2109	2266
Solid thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	1.0	1.0	2
Liquid thermal conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	1.0	1.0	1.885
Solid specific heat capacity (J·kg ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	928	1005	1338.88
Liquid specific heat capacity (J·kg ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	1035	1096	1757.28

Where,

PCM S1: 59.98 wt% MgCl₂ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% NaCl.

PCM S2: 55 wt% MgCl₂ – 45% NaCl.

PCM S3: 35 wt% Li₂CO₃ – 65 wt% K₂CO₃.

3.4.4 PCMs for FLiNaK Salt

Molten FLiNaK salt is preferable to be used as heat transfer fluid (HTF) as it can transfer heat at elevated temperature. Azam and Mamun [96] used FLiNaK salt as HTF to analyze the thermal performance of multi-layer thermal energy storage tank. They used the following thermo-physical properties of the multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) for FLiNaK salt:

Table 3.4 Thermo-physical properties of the multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) for Solar salt [84, 97, 98]:

Arrangement	PCM F1 [84]	PCM F2 [84, 97]	PCM F3 [97, 98]
Melting temperature (°C)	505	580	710
Latent heat of fusion (kJ· kg ⁻¹)	344	288	163
Solid density (kg· m ⁻³)	2266	2340	2400
Solid thermal conductivity (W· m ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹)	2	1.95	1.73
Liquid thermal conductivity (W· m ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹)	1.885	1.95	1.73
Solid specific heat capacity (J· kg ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹)	1338.88	1800	1670
Liquid specific heat capacity (J· kg ⁻¹ · K ⁻¹)	1757.28	2090	1560

Where,

PCM F1: 35 wt%Li₂CO₃ – 65 wt%K₂CO₃.

PCM F2: 22 wt%Li₂CO₃-16 wt%Na₂CO₃-62 wt%K₂CO₃

PCM F3: 51wt% K₂CO₃ and 49 wt%Na₂CO₃.

3.5 Properties of Solid filler materials

Solid rocks are used as filler materials for sensible heat transfer. Thermophysical properties of solid rocks are given below:

Table 3.5 Thermophysical properties of solid rocks [80]

Arrangement	Solid rocks
Density (kg/m^3)	2000
Specific Heat Capacity (J/kg. K)	1500
Thermal Conductivity (W/m. K)	1

Chapter 4

Mathematical Modelling

For any kind of numerical problem, it is necessary to model the problem mathematically. Any physical system can be modeled using one or more algebraic or differential equations. After that, these equations have to be solved using appropriate initial and/or boundary conditions found from the physical problem. Hence, mathematical modeling is the most important part to obtain the accurate and realistic solution of the physical problem.

4.1 Governing Equations

The dispersion-concentric model, based on a special version of the energy equation, is used to construct the computational scheme for this analysis. This is a two-phase model based on the energy equation where the tank is considered as an isotropic porous medium filled with small spherical fragments. Temperature distribution inside spherical particles and axial heat conduction of fluid are taken into consideration in this model. Here is reported how to obtain the system of equations used to describe the model.

4.1.1 Continuity Equation

$$\epsilon \frac{\partial \rho_f}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial \rho_f u_f}{\partial x} \quad (4.1)$$

Continuity equation can also be written as,

$$\frac{\partial \rho_f}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial \rho_f U}{\partial x} \quad (4.2)$$

Where, $u_f = \epsilon U$; U is the intrinsic average velocity, ϵ is the porosity of the bed. u_f has been given various names, by different authors, such as seepage velocity, filtration velocity, superficial velocity, Darcy velocity, and volumetric flux density etc.

4.1.2 Momentum Equation

Darcy's law is an equation that describes the flow of a fluid through a porous medium. The law was formulated by Henry Darcy based on results of experiments on the flow of water through beds of sand, forming the basis of hydrogeology, a branch of earth sciences.

The Darcy's Law of the momentum equation is now discussed which is the porous-medium analog of the Navier–Stokes equation. For the moment, neglecting body forces such as gravity; the appropriate terms for these can be added easily at a later stage.

4.1.2.1 Darcy's Law: Permeability

Henry Darcy's (1856) investigations into the hydrology of the water supply of Dijon and his experiments on steady-state unidirectional flow in a uniform medium revealed a proportionality between flow rate and the applied pressure difference. In modern notation this is expressed, in refined form, by

$$u = - \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (4.3)$$

Here, $\partial P / \partial x$ is the pressure gradient in the flow direction and μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. The coefficient K is independent of the nature of the fluid, but it depends on the geometry of the medium. It has dimensions $(\text{length})^2$ and is called the specific permeability or intrinsic permeability of the medium.

If K is indeed determined by the geometry of the medium, then clearly it is possible to calculate K in terms of the geometrical parameters, at least for the case of simple geometry. A great deal of effort has been spent on this endeavor, and the results are well presented by Dullien [175].

For example, in the case of beds of particles or fibers, one can introduce an effective average particle or fiber diameter d_p . The hydraulic radius theory of Carman–Kozeny leads to the relationship

$$K = \frac{d_p^2}{180} \frac{\epsilon^3}{(1-\epsilon)^2} \quad (4.4)$$

The constant 180 was obtained by seeking a best fit with experimental results. The Carman–Kozeny equation gives satisfactory results for media that consist of particles of approximately spherical shape and whose diameters fall within a narrow range.

4.1.3 Energy equation

Azam et al. [176] as well as other researchers used the Dispersion-Concentric model which consists of the following equations. Energy equation for the liquid phase:

$$\epsilon (\rho_f C_{p_f}) \left(\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + u_f \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right) = \epsilon k_f \frac{\partial^2 T_f}{\partial x^2} + h_f (T_s - T_f) \quad (4.5)$$

Energy equation for the solid phase:

$$(1 - \epsilon) \rho_s C_{p_s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = (1 - \epsilon) k_s \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial x^2} + h_f (T_f - T_s) \quad (4.6)$$

Where T_s and T_f represent the temperature of solid filler materials and heat transfer fluid respectively. The temperature distribution on the surface of the PCM(s) particles can be calculated from:

$$\rho_s C_{p_s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(k_s r^2 \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \right) \quad (4.7)$$

Here, h_f is denoted as volumetric heat transfer coefficient, A critical aspect of using this approach lies in the determination of the appropriate value of h . Experimental values of h are found in an indirect manner; see, e.g., Polyakov et al. (1996). According to correlations for a porous bed of particle established in Dixon and Cresswell (1979),

$$h_f = a_{sf} h \quad (4.8)$$

Where, a_{sf} is the specific surface area that can be expressed as [177]:

$$a_{sf} = \frac{6(1-\epsilon)}{d_p} \quad (4.9)$$

So,

$$h_f = \frac{6(1-\epsilon)}{d_p} h \quad (4.10)$$

Here h refers to the interstitial heat transfer coefficient which can be determined from,

$$\frac{1}{h} = \frac{1}{h_s} + \frac{d_p}{\beta k_s} \quad (4.11)$$

Where d_p stands for the particle diameter and β is 10 for spherical particles. h_s is true heat transfer coefficient between solid and fluid which can be expressed by,

$$h_s = \frac{Nu k}{d_p} \quad (4.12)$$

Nu is the Nusselt number which depends on Reynolds number and Prandtl number [15]:

$$Nu = 2 + 1.1 (Re^{0.6} Pr^{0.33}) \quad (4.13)$$

Here,

$$Re_p = \frac{\rho d_p u_f}{\epsilon \mu} \quad (4.14)$$

Where u_f denotes fluid velocity and

$$Pr = \frac{c_p \mu_f}{k} \quad (4.15)$$

4.2 Total Enthalpy

The internal energy, E_i , is defined as:

$$E_i = H \text{ for solid domains and}$$

$$E_i = H - p/\rho \text{ for fluid domains where } H \text{ is the enthalpy.}$$

The enthalpy can then be retrieved from the following equation:

$$H = H_{ref} + \int_{r_0}^{r_1} \nabla_r H(r) \cdot dr \quad (4.16)$$

where r is the integration vector variable, containing temperature and pressure or stress tensor components:

$$r = \begin{pmatrix} P \\ T \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad r = \begin{pmatrix} P_{11} \\ P_{22} \\ P_{33} \\ P_{12} \\ P_{23} \\ P_{13} \\ T \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.17)$$

The starting point, r_0 , is the value of r at reference conditions, that is, P_{ref} (one atmosphere) and T_{ref} (298.15 K) for a fluid. The ending point, r_1 , is the solution returned after simulation. In theory any value can be assigned to the enthalpy at reference conditions, H_{ref} and it is set to 0 J/kg. The heat capacity at constant pressure is related to the enthalpy, seen as a function of T, according to:

$$\left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \right)_P = C_p \quad (4.18)$$

where the total enthalpy, H_0 , is defined as

$$H_0 = H + \frac{u \cdot u}{2} \quad (4.19)$$

In this research, total enthalpy refers to the summation of the total enthalpy of heat transfer fluid and the total enthalpy filler materials. Here, the unit of total enthalpy is kJ/kg.

4.3 Heat Transfer with Phase Change Materials

The Phase Change Material node is used to solve the heat equation after specifying the properties of a phase change material according to the *apparent heat capacity* formulation.

Instead of adding a latent heat L in the energy balance equation exactly when the material reaches its phase change temperature T_{pc} , it is assumed that the transformation occurs in a temperature interval between $T_{pc} - \Delta T/2$ and $T_{pc} + \Delta T/2$. In this interval, the material phase is modeled by a smoothed function, θ , representing the fraction of phase before transition, which is equal to 1 before $T_{pc} - \Delta T/2$ and to 0 after $T_{pc} + \Delta T/2$. The density, ρ , and the specific enthalpy, H , are expressed by:

$$\rho = \theta \rho_{ph1} + (1 - \theta) \rho_{ph2} \quad (4.20)$$

$$H = \frac{1}{\rho} (\theta \rho_{ph1} H_{ph1} + (1 - \theta) \rho_{ph2} H_{ph2}) \quad (4.21)$$

where the indices ph_1 and ph_2 indicate a material in phase 1 or in phase 2, respectively. Differentiating with respect to temperature, this equality provides the following formula for the specific heat capacity:

$$C_p = \frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \quad (4.22)$$

which becomes, after some formal transformations:

$$C_p = \frac{1}{\rho} (\theta_1 \rho_{ph1} C_{p,ph1} + \theta_2 \rho_{ph2} C_{p,ph2}) + (H_{ph2} - H_{ph1}) \frac{d\alpha_m}{dT} \quad (4.23)$$

Here, θ_1 and θ_2 are equal to θ and $1 - \theta$, respectively. The mass fraction, α_m , is defined from ρ_{ph1} , ρ_{ph2} and θ according to:

$$\alpha_m = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\theta_2 \rho_{ph2} - \theta_1 \rho_{ph1}}{\rho} \quad (4.24)$$

It is equal to $-1/2$ before transformation and $1/2$ after transformation. The specific heat capacity is the sum of an equivalent heat capacity C_{eq} :

$$C_{eq} = \frac{1}{\rho} (\theta_1 \rho_{ph1} C_{p,ph1} + \theta_2 \rho_{ph2} C_{p,ph2}) \quad (4.25)$$

And the distribution of latent heat C_L :

$$C_L(T) = (H_{ph2} - H_{ph1}) \frac{d\alpha_m}{dT} \quad (4.26)$$

The latent heat distribution C_L is approximated by,

$$C_L(T) = L \frac{d\alpha_m}{dT} \quad (4.27)$$

so that the total heat per unit volume released during the phase transformation coincides with the latent heat:

$$\int_{T_{pc} + \frac{\Delta T}{2}}^{T_{pc} + \frac{\Delta T}{2}} C_L(T) dT = L \int_{T_{pc} + \frac{\Delta T}{2}}^{T_{pc} + \frac{\Delta T}{2}} \frac{d\alpha_m}{dT} dT = L \quad (4.28)$$

The latent heat, L , can depend on the absolute pressure but should not depend on the temperature. Finally, the apparent heat capacity, C_p , used in the heat equation, is given by:

$$C_p = \frac{1}{\rho} (\theta_1 \rho_{ph1} C_{p,ph1} + \theta_2 \rho_{ph2} C_{p,ph2}) + C_L \quad (4.29)$$

The effective thermal conductivity reduces to:

$$k = \theta_1 k_{ph1} + \theta_2 k_{ph2} \quad (4.30)$$

And the effective density is:

$$\rho = \theta_1 \rho_{ph1} + \theta_2 \rho_{ph2} \quad (4.31)$$

For PCM in solid phase,

$$T < T_{pc}, \theta_1 = 1, \theta_2 = 0, k = k_s, C_p = C_{ps} \text{ and } \rho = \rho_s$$

For PCM in liquid phase,

$$T > T_{pc}, \theta_1 = 0, \theta_2 = 1, k = k_l, C_p = C_{pl} \text{ and } \rho = \rho_l$$

4.3.1 Effective Thermal Conductivity of Immobile materials

The porous media consists of spherical particles of immobile materials. This can also be considered in the model, and the effective material properties are calculated accordingly. One of the methods of calculating effective thermal conductivity is the volume average method. The volume average thermal conductivity of the porous matrix consisting of different materials can be calculated by the following formula:

$$k_s = \sum_{i=1} \theta_{pi} k_{si} \quad (4.32)$$

Figure 4.2: Schematic diagram of a spherical PCM particles with coating

Let us consider phase change materials (PCM) is confined in different layered spherical shells. So, the final thermal conductivity of the whole sphere k_s can be written as follow, where θ_{p1} , θ_{p2} are volume fractions of shell material and PCM respectively and k_{s1} , k_{s2} are thermal conductivities of the same.

$$k_s = \theta_{p1} k_{s1} + \theta_{p2} k_{s2}$$

$$\theta_{p1} = \frac{V_1}{V}, \theta_{p2} = \frac{V_2}{V} \quad (4.33)$$

V_1 and V_2 are the volume of shell and PCM respectively and V is the total volume.

$$V_1 = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_o^3 - \frac{4}{3} \pi R_i^3 = \frac{4}{3} \pi (R_o^3 - R_i^3) = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_o^3 \left(1 - \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3}\right) \quad (4.34)$$

And,

$$V_2 = \frac{4}{3} \pi R_i^3 \quad (4.35)$$

So, θ_{p1} , θ_{p2} can be written as:

$$\theta_{p1} = \frac{V_1}{V} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi(R_o^3 - R_i^3)}{\frac{4}{3}\pi R_o^3} = \frac{(R_o^3 - R_i^3)}{R_o^3} = 1 - \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3} \quad (4.36)$$

$$\theta_{p2} = 1 - \theta_{p1} = 1 - 1 + \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3} = \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3} \quad (4.37)$$

Thermal conductivity in term of radius can be written as:

$$k_s = \theta_{p1}k_{s1} + \theta_{p2}k_{s2} \quad (4.38)$$

$$k_s = \left(1 - \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3}\right)k_{s1} + \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3}k_{s2} \quad (4.39)$$

If the shell thickness is so small compared with the inner radius, that is,

$$\frac{R_i}{R_o} \approx 1, \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3} \approx 1, \text{ Then, } \theta_{p1} = 0,$$

So,

$$k_s = \theta_{p2}k_{s2} = \frac{R_i^3}{R_o^3}k_{s2} = k_{s2} \quad \left[\frac{R_i}{R_o} \approx 1\right] \quad (4.40)$$

In this research, it was considered that the shell thickness is too small. So, the effective thermal conductivity of the spherical capsule can be considered equal to the thermal conductivity of phase change materials (PCMs).

4.3.2 Thermocline Thickness

Thermocline thickness may be defined as the thickness inside a thermal storage tank where large temperature difference exists. In sensible heat storage tank, there is only one region of thermocline however, in latent heat storage system, more than one zones are observed that all together create the thermocline.

Figure 4.1: Temperature profile and thermocline thickness [178]

The thickness of the thermocline is not easy to determine as there is no definite point from where the temperature starts to decrease drastically (figure 4.1). There is no well-defined formula for the thermocline thickness. Waluyo and Majid [178] formulated thermocline thickness using functional relationship of temperature and identified two functions which could represent S-curve of temperature distribution, namely sigmoid dose response (SDR) and four parameter sigmoid (FPS) functions. Both functions were observed to well fit the temperature distributions having coefficient determination more than 0.99. In this research a simplified formula is given to determine the thermocline thickness based on non-dimensional temperature. The difference between the height of maximum temperature and minimum temperature along tank height is defined as the thermocline thickness. The maximum and minimum temperatures are the temperatures when the non-dimensional temperature difference has the value of 0.99.

The maximum and minimum temperature is defined as follows:

$$\Theta_1 = \frac{T_{max} - T_h}{T_h - T_c} = 0.99 \quad (4.41)$$

$$\Theta_2 = \frac{T_h - T_{min}}{T_h - T_c} = 0.99 \quad (4.42)$$

Where, T_h and T_c are the hot and cold fluid temperatures respectively. The thermocline thickness, W_{TC} can be represented as the function of maximum and minimum temperature.

$$W_{TC} = y(T_{max}) - y(T_{min}) \quad (4.43)$$

Chapter 5

Computational Method

Any mechanical problem can be solved in three different ways, namely experimental, numerical, and analytical approaches. When the equations are more complex, numerical approach is preferable than analytical one. In this chapter, a brief discussion of numerical method is presented. Among different numerical methods, finite element method is applied for the present problem.

5.1 Computational Fluid Dynamics

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is a branch of fluid mechanics that uses numerical analysis and data structures to analyze and solve problems that involve fluid flows. Computers are used to perform the calculations needed to simulate the free-stream flow of the fluid, and the interaction of the fluid (liquids and gases) with surfaces defined by boundary conditions. The fundamental basis of almost all CFD problems is the Navier–Stokes equations, which define many single-phase (gas or liquid, but not both) fluid flows. These equations can be made simple by removing viscosity terms to yield the Euler equations. Further simplification, by removing vorticity terms yields the full potential equations. Finally, for small perturbations in subsonic and supersonic flows, (not transonic or hypersonic) these equations can be linearized to yield the linearized potential equations. CFD provides a qualitative and even quantitative prediction of fluid flows by means of mathematical modeling through formulation of equations, numerical methods through discretization and solution techniques and software tools with solvers, pre and post processing

utilities. Different types of numerical solution procedure are available and among them finite difference, finite element, finite volume, spectral element methods are very popular. All this method can be applied to find out the numerical solution. However, proper choice of the method can reduce the computational time and ensure better numerical accuracy. Although Finite Element Methods have certain limitations, advanced techniques are adopted to overcome those limitations and keep the numerical error in reasonable limit. The numerical solution techniques are getting popular day by day due to their attractive features.

5.2 Computational Heat Transfer

Computational heat transfer (CHT) deals with the energy equations. Over the past twenty years, computational heat transfer has emerged as a new field, which promises to have significant impact on research, design, and education. With the rapid development of computer hardware, the computational techniques for heat transfer and fluid flow have been vigorously proposed, tested, and refined. Practicing engineers and researchers are beginning to recognize computational analysis as a cost-effective and convenient way of obtaining detailed solutions for complex physical situations. Computational heat transfer is a special genre in the field of heat transfer. Equations which can't be solved by analytic approach computational methods are available there as a powerful tool for solving those equations. Like CFD it uses different numerical approach like finite difference method, finite element method, finite volume method, etc.

5.3 Finite Element Method

The finite element method (FEM) has been used for solving differential equations in different engineering and mathematical modeling. The term finite element was first introduced by Clough in 1960. In the early 1960s, this method is used by engineers for approximate solutions of problems in stress analysis, fluid flow, heat transfer, and other areas. The FEM is a particular numerical method for solving partial differential equations in two or three space variables. To solve a problem, the FEM subdivides a large system into smaller, simpler parts that are called finite elements. This is done by a particular space discretization in the space dimensions, which is enforced by the construction of mesh inside the object: the numerical domain for the solution,

which has a certain number of points. Finally, the finite element formulation of a boundary value problem results in a system of algebraic equations. The method approximates the unknown variables at the domain. The simple equations that model these finite elements are then assembled into a larger system of equations that models the entire problem. The FEM then uses variational or weighted residual or direct methods from the calculus to approximate a solution by minimizing an associated error function.

5.3.1 Advantages of Finite Element Method

The advantages of FEM over other methods are stated below:

- Finite Element Method is well-suited for complex geometry than FDM.
- It can handle a wide variety of engineering problems: Solid Mechanics, Fluids, Heat Transfer, Dynamics, Electrostatic problems etc.
- FEM can handle complex restraints and complex loading: Point load, Element load etc. compared with other numerical methods.
- Writing computer codes on FEM is structured and straight forward.
- Conventional numerical solvers can be used to solve the equations generated by FEM.
- FEM can combine different kinds of functions that estimate the solution within each element which is nearly impossible with FDM or FVM.

5.4 Numerical Approach

In this research, a 2D model of thermocline thermal energy storage (TES) tank will be developed which is considered as an isotropic porous medium filled with distinct solid spherical particles. A numerical model will be built that describes the way of traveling heat through the thermocline TES tank. Continuity and Momentum equations in the porous medium will be used for this system to get the flow pattern. The heat transfer module of this numerical model is developed by a special form of energy equation called Dispersion-Concentric (D-C) equation. As the tank is cylindrical and symmetric about its axis so the equations are solved for only the half portion of the tank. To solve the problem, our given system will be subdivided into smaller, simpler parts. This will be

achieved by a particular space discretization in the space dimensions, which will be implemented by the construction of a mesh of the object. The Finite Element Method (FEM) formulation of a boundary value problem will be used to solve these equations. For time-dependent equations, an implicit method, Backward differentiation formula (BDF) will be used. The work will be done both for charging and discharging cycles of the heat transfer fluid through the TES and LHTES tanks. Different heat transfer media as well as different filler materials will be required in the tank to observe the change in the graph. The predicted results will be compared with the numerical results from the published literature to validate the mathematical model and the numerical scheme. Finally, two-dimensional graphical representation of isothermal contour, streamline etc. can be shown and the relation between temperature with time and space will be presented. To simplify the analysis, the model is based on the following assumptions:

1. The heat transfer module is symmetric about its axis.
2. The numerical model does not contain any distributors.
3. The tank is considered to be a homogeneous porous medium filled with continuous, isotropic solid particles.
4. The flow of heat transfer fluid inside the TES tank is laminar and incompressible.
5. The properties of HTF are functions of temperature while the solid particles have constant properties.
6. The value of latent heat is considered to be equal both in melting and solidification.
7. Radiation heat transfer inside the tank is neglected and no internal heat generation is considered.
8. The effective thermal conductivity of the immobile materials is equals to the thermal conductivity of phase change materials.

5.4.1 Flow Chart:

Figure 5.1: Flow chart of the numerical process

5.5 Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions of the TES tank are given below.

For fluid flow:

1. Body force is neglected. i.e., $\mathbf{F}=\mathbf{0}$
2. Near the tank wall, no slip condition is applied i.e., $\mathbf{u}_f = \mathbf{0}$ at $r = D/2$
3. At inlet, the mass flow rate boundary condition sets the total mass flow through the boundary according to:

$$-\int_{\partial\Omega} d_{bc}\rho(\mathbf{u}\cdot\mathbf{n}) dS = m$$

Where d_{bc} (only present in the 2D Cartesian axis system) is the boundary thickness normal to the fluid-flow domain and m is the total mass flow rate. In addition to the constraint on the total flow across the boundary, the tangential velocity components are set to zero on the boundary

$$\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{0}$$

4. For single-phase flow, a mathematically correct natural boundary condition with suppress backflow option for outlets is:

$$\begin{aligned} (p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T))\mathbf{n} &= -\hat{p}_0\mathbf{n} \\ \text{where, } \hat{p}_0 &\leq p_0 \end{aligned}$$

For heat transfer in solid and fluid:

1. Thermal insulation is considered near the tank wall. i.e.,

$$-\mathbf{n}\cdot\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}$$

5.6 Mesh generation

Mesh generation is the practice of creating a mesh, a subdivision of a continuous geometric space into discrete geometric and topological cells. Often these cells form a simplicial complex. Usually, the cells partition the geometric input domain. Mesh cells are used as discrete local approximations of the larger domain. In the present study, the given model was subdivided into smaller and simpler parts by the ‘‘Quadrilateral Meshing’’ scheme to generate the mesh. A ‘‘Quadrilateral mesh’’ is a

dense mesh describing a topologically continuous surface of 4-corner primitives. i.e., a grid, without the “regular”. This is useful particularly when combined with map projections and texture mapping. As the geometry of the model is rectangular in shape, so the quad shape will provide the best matches for generating the mesh. Although triangle meshes are the most popular representations, quadrilateral meshes have many advantages and have been widely used CAD and simulation. The main advantages of quad-meshes can be summarized as follows:

1. Quad-mesh can better capture the local principal curvature directions or sharp features, as well as the semantics of modeled objects, therefore it is widely used in animation industry.
2. Quad-mesh has tensor product structure, it is suitable for fitting splines or NURBS. Therefore, it is applied for high-order surface modeling, such as CAD/CAM for Splines and NURBS, and the entertainment industry for subdivision surfaces.
3. Patches of semi-regular quad meshes with a rectangular grid topology, naturally match the sampling pattern of textures. Therefore, quad mesh is highly preferred for texturing and compression.
4. The Quad mesh (Structured) can provide better results at higher-order schemes and still retaining better numerical stability and accuracy.

Denser mesh is used near the wall of the tank to find the accurate flow pattern. Complete mesh consists of 6200 domain elements and 324 boundary elements. Some of the main parameters of quad mesh are listed below in the following table:

Table 5.1 Some of the main mesh parameters

Mesh Parameters	Values
Maximum element size	0.01 m
Minimum element size	1×10^{-4} m
Maximum element growth rate	1.1
Curvature factor	0.25
Number of vertex elements	4
Minimum element quality	0.9083

Figure 5.2: 2D Mesh inside the tank geometry

Figure 5.2 represents the two-dimensional mesh formulation inside the storage tank. Identifying the mesh best suited for a particular model often involves choosing the correct element types and sizes. “Quadrilateral Meshing” scheme is used to generate mesh in the present study. As the model is axisymmetric about its axis, mesh is generated only for the right half portion of the tank. Maximum element growth rate refers how the element size can grow from a region with small elements to a region with larger elements. The value must be greater or equal to one. In this study maximum element growth rate is 1.1, that means the element size can grow by at most 10% (approximately) from one element to another.

The curvature factor is the ratio between the boundary element size and the curvature radius. The curvature radius multiplied by the curvature factor, which must be a positive scalar, gives the maximum allowed element size along the boundary. A smaller curvature factor gives a finer mesh along curved boundaries.

(b)

Figure 5.3: Mesh near the tank wall

Figure 5.3 shows the mesh orientation near the boundary of the tank. A boundary layers mesh with dense element distribution in the normal direction along specific boundaries is typically used for fluid flow problems to resolve the thin boundary layers along the no-slip boundaries. In 2D, a layered quadrilateral mesh is used along the specified no-slip boundaries.

5.7 Mesh Independence Test

Figure 5.4: Effect of temperature against tank wall at 20 minutes using Hitec salt solid rock for different mesh sizes.

Figure 5.4 shows the variation of temperature along tank wall at 20 minutes using Hitec salt solid rock for different mesh sizes. Three different maximum mesh sizes are used to plot the graph. One is 0.1 m and another two are 20% larger and 20% smaller respectively. As the graphs obtained by using three different mesh sizes don't show large variation mesh all the three meshes are within acceptable ranges. In the current study, maximum mesh size is used 0.1 m.

5.8 Model Validation

The numerical method is validated with published literature to accomplish the results of our study. The numerical results of Elfeki et al. [177] are used to validate our numerical model. Figure 5.4 (a) is the graphical representation of molten salt temperature along the centerline with normalized tank height. Figure 5.5 (b) shows the temperature variation with normalized bed height for the current study. To validate our numerical method, we used similar data from the work of literature of Elfeki et al. [177]. The two figures assert that the numerical result obtained from the present study is closer to the results of the literature. For validation purpose, phase change materials of 59.98 wt% MgCl_2 – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% NaCl was used as filler materials and solar slat was used as heat transfer media which is a mixture of 60 wt.% NaNO_3 and 40 wt.% KNO_3 . The inlet temperature of hot molten salt was 565 °C used in the paper where the temperature of cold molten

salt was 288 °C. As the numerical result obtained by the present study is compatible with the numerical result of Elfeki et al. [177] so our method of solving the given equations is considered to be acceptable.

Figure 5.5: (a) Graphical representation of temperature versus normalized bed height from the work of Elfeki et al. [177], (b): Temperature variation along normalized bed height represented in the current study.

Figure 5.6: Graphical representation of temperature versus normalized bed height from the work of Elfeki et al. [177] and present study in the same plot

Figure 5.7: Graphical representation of temperature versus tank axial distance from the work of Xu et al. [135] and present study in the same plot

Figure 5.7 shows the effect of temperature on tank axial distance from the work of Xu et al. [135] and compares with the present study in the same plot. The graphs are plotted for solid rocks not for phase change materials. Xu et al. validated his graph with the work Pacheco et al. which is seen in the figure. The broken lines represent the graph of Pacheco et al. and the square dash lines represents the plot of Xu et al. The graph obtained by using the formulation of the present study is demonstrated by asterisk sign. Pacheco obtained his graph by experimental method and many researchers used this graph for the validation of their results. However, Xu et al. found his graph by numerical simulation. The present study shows good agreement with both the graphs. So, the method of solving the equations in the current work is considered to be accepted.

Chapter 6

Results

The main objectives of the study are to perform numerical simulations of single layered and multi-layered PCM(s) in TES tank using different heat transfer fluids and to determine the effect of using different PCM(s) as well as different heat transfer media on temperature in the TES tank. The prescribed objectives are fulfilled in this section and temperature distribution of different HTF and filler materials as a function of time and position are also observed. Finally, a comparative study has been made among the alternatives based on the amount of heat transfer and energy efficiency.

6.1 Velocity and Pressure for charging cycle

In this section, the velocity, pressure, and streamline diagram for the combination of Hitec salt and PCM H1 is shown for charging cycle. Hitec salt is used as the heat transfer fluid and PCM H1 is selected to be used as filler materials. The pattern of these diagrams is almost equal to other diagrams obtained from other combinations of HTF and filler materials. These diagrams are enough to understand the pattern of fluid flow, velocity pressure and streamline inside the TES tank.

Velocity profile is an important tool for understanding and visualizing the flow pattern. From simulation, the velocity magnitude of each material can be found up to 210 minutes. The flow pattern is almost same throughout the charging cycle. So, the velocity profile, pressure contour and streamline are shown at 210 minutes.

Figure 6.1: (a) Velocity magnitude over the entire surface of the TES tank, (b) Extended velocity diagram near the Tank wall during charging cycle

Figure 6.2: Pressure contour inside the TES tank for charging cycle

Figure 6.1 shows the velocity magnitude inside the TES tank for charging cycle. In the charging cycle, hot fluid flows from top surface to bottom surface. Figure 6.1 (a) shows the velocity magnitude for the whole tank and Figure 6.1 (b) shows the zoomed in diagram near the tank wall. In this diagram, the variation of velocity magnitude near the boundary of the tank is seen, but this

variation takes place only in a narrow area close to the border. For better understanding, the velocity magnitude is demonstrated by color code. Red color represents the higher velocity where blue color represents the lower velocity. The maximum velocity inside the tank is 0.37 mm/s.

Figure 6.2 show the pressure contour inside the TES tank and the pressure is gauge pressure. Pressure contour is an isobaric line where pressure is same along the line. From the figure it can be observed that the pressure is slightly higher near the top surface of the tank and slightly lower near the bottom surface of the tank. The pressure at the top of the tank is 388 Pa and at the bottom the value is around 5 Pa. The pressure difference between the top surface and the bottom surface is nearly about 383 Pa which is comparatively very low than atmospheric pressure.

Figure 6.3: Streamline inside the TES tank for charging cycle

Figure 6.3 represents the streamline inside the TES tank and arrow line shows the direction of the flow. From the streamlines it can be understood that the flow is laminar throughout the tank and there is no turbulence created inside the tank. Arrow lines represents that the fluid flows towards downwards.

6.2 Velocity and Pressure for Discharging Cycle

Figure 6.4: (a) Velocity magnitude (mm/s) over the entire surface of the TES tank, (b) Extended near the Tank wall for discharging cycle

Figure 6.5: Pressure contour inside the TES tank for discharging cycle

Figure 6.4 shows the velocity magnitude inside the TES tank during discharging cycle. Discharging cycle is the opposite of charging cycle. In the discharging cycle, hot fluid flows from the bottom surface of the tank to the top surface. Figure 6.4 (a) shows the velocity magnitude for the whole tank and Figure 6.4 (b) shows the zoomed in diagram near the tank wall. Like charging

cycle, in this diagram, the variation of velocity magnitude is seen near the boundary of the tank, but this variation takes place only in a narrow area close to the border. For better understanding, the velocity magnitude is demonstrated by color code. The maximum velocity inside the tank is 0.31 mm/s.

Figure 6.6: Streamline inside the TES tank for discharging cycle

Figure 6.5 show the pressure contour inside the TES tank and the pressure is gauge pressure. Unlike charging cycle, the pressure is slightly higher near the bottom surface of the tank as the fluid enters from the bottom side of the tank and slightly lower near the top surface of the tank. The pressure at the bottom of the tank is 388 Pa and at the top the value is around 5 Pa. The pressure difference between the top surface and the bottom surface is nearly about 383 Pa which is also comparatively low.

Figure 6.6 represents the streamline inside the TES tank and upward arrow line shows the direction of the flow. The fluid direction is opposite to the direction of charging cycle.

6.3 Temperature profile for charging cycle

Temperature profile is a powerful tool in the analysis of heat transfer as it refers to the temperature distribution of each small parts of the 2D geometry. As transient heat transfer is analyzed, temperature of every single element of mesh as well as for every definite time interval can be found. In this section, temperature distribution along bed height has been demonstrated for different time interval. Surface temperature of TES tank for different heat transfer fluids is demonstrated for their respective phase change materials (PCMs). Along with the surface temperature profile line graph is also plotted simultaneously to understand how temperature profiles are created.

As the tank is axially symmetric, simulation is done for the half portion of the TES tank. So, the pattern is noticed for the half part of the tank. The 2D surface temperature sketch inside the TES tank represents the real scenario of flow illustrated by different color codes. Simulation is performed from 0 minutes to 210 minutes. So, it can be easily understood and visualized the temperature profile inside the tank at different time.

6.3.1 Temperature Profile for Hitec Salt

In this section, the temperature profile showed is constructed by using molten Hitec salt as heat transfer fluid. The temperature range for this salt is used 210 °C to 500 °C. PCM H1, PCM H2, PCM H3, the combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are used as filler materials. The temperature profile is shown for 0 minutes, 20 minutes, 60 minutes, and 80 minutes.

The first three sub-sections under this section represent the single stage thermal energy storage tank that means the whole tank is filled with single type phase change materials. In the fourth sub-section three-stage PCM system is represented and discussed. In three stage PCM, the whole tank is subdivided into three different levels. The bottom level is filled with PCM H1, the middle level is filled with PCM H2 and the top level is filled with PCM H3. The PCMs are arranged in such a way that the PCM of lowest melting point is kept at the bottom level of the tank and the PCM of the highest melting point is kept at the top position of the tank. So, when the heat transfer fluid enters the tank, the top level PCM melts first, then middle level PCM melts and finally the bottom level PCM melts.

6.3.1.1 PCM H1

Figure 6.7 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for PCM H1 i.e., PCM H1 ($\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-K}_2\text{CO}_3$) is used as filler materials.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.7: (a-e) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes respectively for PCM H1, (f-j) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 minutes respectively

In the Figure 6.7, (a-e) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.7 (f-j) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. Blue color is the sign of cold temperature and red color is the sign of high temperature. At 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 210 °C. However, a very small temperature gradient is seen at the topmost position of the tank. This gradient is seen, as at that time hot fluid is about to enter the tank and just touches the cold fluid surface. At 20 minutes a thermocline zone is visible near 0.8 m height of the TES tank. The temperature changes more quickly near the 0.8 m tank height in the Figure 6.7 (a) at 20 minutes than in any other

position in the thermocline TES tank. This rapid change of temperature is called the thermocline. Similarly, at 40 minutes, 60 minutes and 80 minutes thermocline takes place near 0.5 m, 0.3m and 0.1 m respectively. The Steeper curve of temperature is the sign of a thinner thermocline zone. A thinner thermocline zone is more desirable because if the zone is thinner less heat will be transferred to the cold fluid. However, as time progresses, the thermocline region flattens as the heat gets more time to transfer from hot fluid to cold one. Above the thermocline zone, the temperature is equal to the inlet temperature and below the zone, it's just cold fluid of lower temperature.

Figure 6.8: (a) Effect of temperature on tank axial distance of TES tank for PCM H1 (b) Domain temperature against time of the TES tank for PCM H1

Figure 6.8 (a) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60, 80 minutes). PCM H1 is used as filler materials and molten Hitec salt is used as heat transfer media here. Figure 6.8 (b) is the graphical representation of domain temperature against time. Domain temperature is the average temperature of the entire tank at a definite time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 210 °C. Because currently the temperature of whole tank is 210 °C. As time passes by hot fluid enters the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. After a certain time when hot fluid replaces the entire cold fluid of the TES tank the domain temperature equals to the hot fluid temperature. For molten Hitec salt and PCM H1 the final domain temperature is 500 °C.

6.3.1.2 PCM H2

Figure 6.9 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for PCM H2 i.e., PCM H2 (59.98 wt% $MgCl_2$ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% $NaCl$) is used as filler materials.

Figure 6.9: (a-e) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes respectively for PCM H2, (f-j) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 minutes respectively

In the Figure 6.9, (a-e) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.9 (f-j) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. Blue color is the sign of cold temperature and red color is the sign of high temperature. At 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 210 °C. At 20 minutes a thermocline zone is visible between 0.7 and 0.8 m height of the TES tank. The temperature changes more quickly at this height of the tank. Similarly, at 40 minutes, 60 minutes and 80 minutes thermocline takes place near 0.5 m, 0.3m and 0.1 m respectively.

Figure 6.10 (a) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60, 80 minutes). PCM H2 is used as filler materials and molten Hitec salt is used as heat transfer media here.

Figure 6.10: (a) Effect of temperature on tank axial distance of TES tank for PCM H2 (b) Domain temperature against time of the TES tank for PCM H2

Figure 6.10 (b) is the graphical representation of domain temperature against time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 210 °C. As time passes by hot fluid enters into the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. For molten Hitec salt and PCM H2 the final domain temperature is 500 °C.

6.3.1.3 PCM H3

Figure 6.11 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for PCM H3 i.e., PCM H3 (55 wt% $MgCl_2$ – 45%NaCl) is used as filler materials.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.11: (a-e) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes respectively for PCM H3, (f-i) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 minutes respectively

In the Figure 6.11, (a-e) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.11 (f-j) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. At 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 210 °C. At 20 minutes a thermocline zone is visible between 0.8 and 0.9 m height of the TES tank. The temperature changes more quickly at this height of the tank. Similarly, at 40 minutes, 60 minutes and 80 minutes thermocline takes place near 0.7 m, 0.5 m and 0.4 m respectively.

Figure 6.12: (a) Effect of temperature on tank axial distance of TES tank for PCM H3 (b) Domain temperature against time of the TES tank for PCM H3

Figure 6.12 (a) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60, 80 minutes). PCM H3 is used as filler materials and molten Hitec salt is used as heat transfer media here. Figure 6.12 (b) is the graphical representation of domain temperature against time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 210 °C. As time passes by hot fluid enters the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. For molten Hitec salt and PCM H3 the final domain temperature is 500 °C.

6.3.1.4 Combination of The Three PCMs

Figure 6.13 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for the combination of the three PCMs. As stated earlier, for the multi-layer phase change materials (MLPCMs) the whole tank is divided into different levels. Here, for three stage PCM system the tank is divided into three levels: the bottom level is filled with PCM H1, the middle level is filled with PCM H2 and the top level is filled with PCM H3.

As three different levels are available here, so three different thermocline layers (also known as pinch point interface) is observed because when hot fluid gradually fills the tank, all the PCMs start melting.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

(d)

(i)

(e)

(j)

Figure 6.13: (a-e) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes respectively for PCM H3, (f-j) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 minutes respectively

Figure 6.13, (a-e) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.13 (f-j) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. In the three-layer TES tank, low melting point PCM is laid down at the bottom of the tank and above this layer PCM with a higher melting point is kept and PCM with the highest melting point is kept on the top position. So, when high-temperature heat transfer fluid flows through the tank firstly the top layer PCM melts, then the lower layer and so on. In the three-layer TES tank, several thermozone zones are created. As shown in Figure 6.13 and 6.14 (a) at 20 and 40 minutes the three layers of thermozone are fairly

noticed, but at 60 minutes upper two layers of thermozone are about to diminished as hot fluid already covers them.

Figure 6.14: (a) Effect of temperature on tank axial distance of TES tank for the combination of three PCM (b) Domain temperature against time of the TES tank

Figure 6.14 (a) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60, 80 minutes). Figure 6.14 (b) is the graphical representation of domain temperature against time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 210 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the final domain temperature is 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

6.3.1.5 Solid Rocks

Figure 6.15 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for solid rocks i.e., solid rock is used as filler materials. In the Figure 6.15, (a-d) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.15 (e-h) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. At 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 210 °C. Unlike other figures the thermocline zone is wider. So, it is hard to locate the exact position of thermocline and this wider zone makes solid rocks less desirable than phase change materials.

(a)

(e)

(b)

(f)

Figure 6.15: (a-d) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40 and 60 minutes respectively for solid rocks, (e-h) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40 and 60 minutes respectively

Figure 6.16: (a) Effect of temperature on tank axial distance of TES tank for solid rocks (b) Domain temperature against time of the TES tank

Figure 6.16 (a) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 minutes). Solid rock is used as filler materials and molten Hitec salt is used as heat transfer media here. Figure 6.16 (b) is the graphical representation of domain temperature against time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 210 °C. As time passes by hot fluid enters the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. For molten Hitec salt and solid rock the final domain temperature is 500 °C.

6.3.2 Temperature Profile for Solar Salt

In this section, the temperature profile we showed is constructed by using molten Solar salt as heat transfer fluid. The working temperature range for this salt is from 280 °C to 570 °C. PCM S1, PCM S2, PCM S3 and the combination of the three PCMs as well as solid particles are used as filler materials. The temperature profile is shown for 0 minutes, 20 minutes, 40 minutes, 60 minutes and 80 minutes.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.17: (a-e) Comparison of charging HTF-temperature profile of a single-PCM S1, PCM S2, PCM S3, Three-stage PCMs and solid rocks for Solar salt, (f-j) domain temperature against time along tank height

Figure 6.17 (a-e) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes). Graph for PCM S1(59.98 wt% $MgCl_2$ – 20.42% KCl – 19.6% $NaCl$), PCM S2(55 wt% $MgCl_2$ – 45% $NaCl$), PCM S3 (35 wt% Li_2CO_3 – 65 wt% K_2CO_3), combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are demonstrated accordingly. For all PCM's, at 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 280 °C. At 20 minutes a pinch point interface zone (also defined

as thermocline zone) is visible near 0.7 m height of the TES tank for PCM S1, 0.8 m height for PCM S2, 0.9 m height for PCM S3. In a similar manner other thermocline zones are created.

For the three stage PCM in figure 6.17 (d) it is seen that, there are several thermocline zones between 40 and 60 minutes. These thermocline zones are created due to the different thermophysical properties of different phase change materials (PCM) layer. Solid rock has the widest thermocline zone. Unlike other figures, the thermocline zone of solid rock is wider inside the tank. So, it is hard to locate the exact position of thermocline and this wider zone makes solid rocks less desirable than phase change materials. Wider thermocline layer is less preferred as the thermocline zone gets wider, maintaining thermal stratification is more difficult. So usable heat is lost from the hot fluid.

Figure 6.17 (f-j) are the graphical representations of domain average temperature against time. Initially, the temperature of TES tank is 280 °C. At time passes by hot fluid enters the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. From figure 6.17 (h) the domain temperature graph changes its gradient near 505°C. The reason is 505°C is the phase change temperature of the PCM S3 and at this temperature the heat transfer continues however, the temperature of PCM S3 doesn't increase. So, the overall temperature of the TES tank doesn't increase rapidly like it increases before 505°C and thus a gradual slope is noticed after 505°C. For molten Solar salt the final domain temperature is 570 °C.

6.3.3 Temperature Profile for FLiNaK Salt

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.18: (a-e) Comparison of charging HTF-temperature profile of a single-PCM-1, PCM-2, PCM-3, Three-stage PCMs and solid rocks for Hitec salt, (f-j) domain temperature graph against time along tank height

Figure 6.18 (a-e) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes). Graph for PCM F1(35 wt%Li₂CO₃ – 65 wt%K₂CO₃), PCM F2 (22 wt%Li₂CO₃-16 wt%Na₂CO₃-62 wt%K₂CO₃), PCM F3 (51wt% K₂CO₃ and 49 wt%Na₂CO₃), combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are demonstrated accordingly. For all PCM's, at 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 475 °C. At 40 minutes a thermocline zone

is visible near 0.5 m height of the TES tank for PCM F1, 0.6 m height for PCM F2, 0.9 m height for PCM S3. In a similar manner other thermocline zones are created.

For the three stage PCM in figure 6.18 (d) it is seen that, there are several thermocline zones between 40 and 60 minutes. These thermocline zones are created due to the different thermophysical properties of different phase change materials (PCM) layer. Solid rock has the widest thermocline zone. Unlike other figures, the thermocline zone of solid rock is wider inside the tank. So, it is hard to locate the exact position of thermocline and this wider zone makes solid rocks less desirable than phase change materials. Wider thermocline layer is less preferred as the thermocline zone gets wider, maintaining thermal stratification is more difficult. So usable heat is lost from the hot fluid.

Figure 6.18 (f-j) are the graphical representations of domain temperature against time. Initially, the temperature of TES tank is 280 °C. At time passes by hot fluid enters the tank and cold fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature increases. For molten Solar salt the final domain temperature is 765 °C.

6.4 Temperature profile for discharging cycle

In this section, temperature distribution along bed height have been demonstrated for different time interval for discharging. In the discharging cycle heat transfer fluid flows from the bottom surface of the TES tank. Surface temperature of TES tank for different heat transfer fluids is demonstrated for their respective phase change materials (PCMs). Along with the surface temperature profile line graph are also plotted simultaneously. So, it can be understood that how temperature profiles are created.

6.4.1 Temperature Profile for Hitec Salt

In this section, the temperature profile showed here is constructed by using molten Hitec salt as heat transfer fluid. The temperature range for this salt is between 500 °C and 210 °C. PCM H1, PCM H2, PCM H3, the combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are used as filler materials. The temperature profile is shown for 0 minutes, 20 minutes, 60 minutes, and 80 minutes.

Figure 6.19 shows the temperature distribution inside the thermal energy storage (TES) tank for PCM H1 i.e., PCM H1 ($\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{CO}_3\text{-K}_2\text{CO}_3$) is used as filler materials. In the Figure 6.13, (a-e) represent the temperature of 2D domain of the TES tank and Figure 6.19 (f-j) demonstrate the line diagram of the respective 2D diagram. Blue color is the sign of cold temperature and red color is the sign of high temperature. At 0 minutes the temperature of whole TES tank is in the initial condition that means the temperature inside the tank is 500 °C. At 20 minutes a thermocline zone is visible near 0.2 m height of the TES tank. The temperature changes more quickly near the 0.2 m tank height in the Figure 6.19 (a) at 20 minutes than in any other position in the thermocline TES tank. This rapid change of temperature is called the thermocline. Similarly, at 40 minutes, 60 minutes and 80 minutes thermocline takes place near 0.3 m, 0.5 m and 0.7 m respectively. The Steeper curve of temperature is the sign of a thinner thermocline zone. A thinner thermocline zone is more desirable because if the zone is thinner less heat will be transferred to the cold fluid. However, as time progresses, the thermocline region flattens as the heat gets more time to transfer from hot fluid to cold one. Below the thermocline zone, the temperature is equal to the inlet temperature and above the zone, it's just hot fluid of higher temperature.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.19: (a-e) 2D representation of temperature profile inside the TES tank at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 minutes respectively for PCM H1, (f-j) line diagram of temperature against tank height inside the TES tank for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 minutes respectively

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

(c)

(h)

Figure 6.20: (a-e) Comparison of charging HTF-temperature profile of a single-PCM H1, PCM H2, PCM H3, Three-stage PCMs and solid rocks for Hitec salt, (f-j) domain temperature graph along tank height

Figure 6.20 (a-e) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 minutes). Temperature profiles of PCM H1, PCM H2, PCM H3, three stage PCM and solid rocks are demonstrated in the figure 6.20 from (a) to (e) respectively. From the figure 6.20 (a-e) it is found that thermocline takes place at different positions at the same time for different filler materials. This behavior depends on the properties of filler materials. Filler

materials having more thermal conductivity transfers more heat than other materials. The speed of the thermocline zone inside the TES tank for a definite heat transfer fluid is a function of thermal conductivity, heat capacity, latent heat of fusion and density of the filler materials. Here, it should be noted that these properties of filler materials depend on temperature and changes the value if phase of the materials is changes.

Figure 6.20 (f-j) represents the domain temperature along tank height for discharging cycle. Domain temperature is the average temperature of the entire tank at a definite time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 500 °C. Because currently the temperature of whole tank is 500 °C. At time passes by cold fluid enters the tank and hot fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature decreases. After a certain period when cold fluid replaces the entire hot fluid of the TES tank, the domain temperature equals to the cold fluid temperature. For molten Hitec salt the final domain temperature is 210 °C.

6.4.2 Temperature Profile for Solar Salt

In this section, the temperature profile we showed is constructed by using molten Solar salt as heat transfer fluid. The temperature range for this salt is used 570 °C to 280 °C. PCM S1, PCM S2, PCM S3, the combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are used as filler materials. The temperature profile is shown for 0 minutes, 20 minutes, 40 minutes, and 60 minutes.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

Figure 6.21: (a-e) Comparison of charging HTF-temperature profile of a single-PCM-1, PCM-2, PCM-3, Three-stage PCMs and solid rocks for Solar salt, (f-j) domain temperature graph along tank height

Figure 6.21 (a-e) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 minutes). Temperature profiles of PCM S1, PCM S2, PCM S3, three stage PCM and solid rocks are demonstrated in the figure 6.21 from (a) to (e) respectively. From the figure 6.21 (a-e) it is found that thermocline takes place at different positions at the same time for different filler materials. This behavior depends on the properties of filler materials. Filler materials having more thermal conductivity transfers more heat than other materials. The speed of the thermocline zone inside the TES tank for a definite heat transfer fluid is a function of thermal conductivity, heat capacity, latent heat of fusion and density of the filler materials. Here, it should be noted that these properties of filler materials depend on temperature and changes the value if phase of the materials is changes.

Figure 6.21 (f-j) represents the domain temperature along tank height for discharging cycle. Domain temperature is the average temperature of the entire tank at a definite time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 570 °C. Because currently the temperature of whole tank is 570 °C. At time passes by cold fluid enters the tank and hot fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature decreases. After a certain period when cold fluid replaces the entire hot fluid of the TES tank, the domain temperature equals to the cold fluid temperature. For molten Hitec salt the final domain temperature is 280 °C.

6.4.3 Temperature Profile for FLiNaK Salt

In this section, the temperature profile we showed is constructed by using molten Solar salt as heat transfer fluid. The temperature range for this salt is used 765 °C to 475 °C. PCM F1, PCM F2, PCM F3, the combination of the three PCMs and solid rocks are used as filler materials. The temperature profile is shown for 0 minutes, 20 minutes, 40 minutes, and 60 minutes.

(a)

(f)

(b)

(g)

Figure 6.22: (a-e) Comparison of charging HTF-temperature profile of a single-PCM F1, PCM F2, PCM F3, Three-stage PCMs and solid rocks for FLiNaK salt, (f-j) domain temperature graph along tank height

Figure 6.22 (a-e) shows the temperature distribution over axial tank height for the combinations of all time periods (0, 20, 40, 60 minutes). Temperature profiles of PCM F1, PCM F2, PCM F3, three stage PCM and solid rocks are demonstrated in the figure 6.22 from (a) to (e) respectively.

From the figure 6.22 (a-e) it is found that thermocline takes place at different positions at the same time for different filler materials. This behavior depends on the properties of filler materials. Filler materials having more thermal conductivity transfers more heat than other materials. The speed of the thermocline zone inside the TES tank for a definite heat transfer fluid is a function of thermal conductivity, heat capacity, latent heat of fusion and density of the filler materials. Here, it should be noted that these properties of filler materials depend on temperature and changes the value if phase of the materials is changes.

Figure 6.22 (f-j) represents the domain temperature along tank height for discharging cycle. Domain temperature is the average temperature of the entire tank at a definite time. At 0 minutes the domain temperature is 765 °C. Because currently the temperature of whole tank is 765 °C. At time passes by cold fluid enters the tank and hot fluid exits from the tank, so the average temperature decreases. After a certain period when cold fluid replaces the entire hot fluid of the TES tank, the domain temperature equals to the cold fluid temperature. For molten FLiNaK salt the final domain temperature is 475 °C.

6.5 Nusselt number for charging cycle

Figure 6.23: Nusselt number for Hitec salt by using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.24: Nusselt number for Solar salt by using (a) PCM S1, (b) PCM S2, (c) PCM S3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.25: Nusselt number for FLiNaK salt by using (a) PCM F1, (b) PCM F2, (c) PCM F3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.26 (a): Variation of Nusselt number for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.26 (b): Variation of Nusselt number for Solar salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.26 (c): Variation of Nusselt number for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for charging cycle

The Nusselt number (Nu) is the ratio of convective to conductive heat transfer at a boundary in a fluid. Convection includes both advection (fluid motion) and diffusion (conduction). The conductive component is measured under the same conditions as the convective but for a hypothetically motionless fluid. It is a dimensionless number, closely related to the fluid's Rayleigh number.

A Nusselt number of values one (1) represents heat transfer by pure conduction. A value between one and 10 is characteristic of slug flow or laminar flow. A larger Nusselt number corresponds to more active convection, with turbulent flow typically in the 100–1000 range. The Nusselt number is named after Wilhelm Nusselt, who made significant contributions to the science of convective heat transfer.

Figure 6.23-6.25 represent the variation of Nusselt number against time for charging cycle. Figure 6.23, Figure 6.24, and Figure 6.25 show the result for Hitec salt, Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. In each figure, a set of five figures is represented for Nusselt number. In a set of figures, the first figure is portrayed for PCM 1. Second, third, fourth and fifth figures show the results for PCM 2, PCM 3, three-layer PCM and solid materials respectively.

In the Figure 6.23 the highest value of Nusselt number is 19.404. Similarly in the Figure 6.24 and Figure 6.25 the highest values of Nusselt numbers are 18.64 and 15.47 respectively. From the range of Nusselt number it can be understood that heat is transferred by both conduction and convection. However, convection heat transfer is dominant here. As we know that if the channel geometry is unchanged the value of Nusselt number is constant for fully developed flow. So, these figures help us to know that where the flow becomes fully developed.

From the figure 26 (a-c), it is seen that for a definite molten salt the Nusselt number starts from a single point and ends in a single line. The reason is clear as the Nusselt number is a function of Reynolds number and Prandtl number, both of which are non-dimensional numbers that depend on temperature. So, all the Nusselt number of different PCMs as well as their combination show almost similar trends in the plot for a particular heat transfer fluid. At 0-minutes Nusselt number has a definite value because of the non-zero value of the Prandtl number at this moment.

6.6 Nusselt number for discharging cycle

Figure 6.27: Nusselt number for Hitec salt by using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.28: Nusselt number for Solar salt by using (a) PCM S1, (b) PCM S2, (c) PCM S3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.29: Nusselt number for FLiNaK salt by using (a) PCM F1, (b) PCM F2, (c) PCM F3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.30 (a): Variation of Nusselt number for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.30 (b): Variation of Nusselt number for Solar salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.30 (c): Variation of Nusselt number for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Nusselt number against time for discharging cycle are portrayed from the Figure 6.27 to Figure 6.29. Figure 6.27 represents a set of figures of the Nusselt number for Solar salt for different filler materials. In every set of figures, there are five subfigures that are denoted by a, b, c, d, and e that refer PCM 1, PCM 2, PCM 3, three-stage PCM and solid materials respectively.

Discharging is a process where hot molten salt is extracted from the tank for the purpose of power generation. Nusselt number is a non-dimensional number and the value of it decreases with time for the TES tank. As phase change materials (PCM) changes its phase from liquid to solid, decrease of Nusselt number is an indication of the effect of conduction heat transfer is increasing with respect to the convection heat transfer. It also indicates that the heat transfer is mostly dominated by conduction for lower Nusselt number.

We have sufficient data of Nusselt number for the charging and discharging cycle. From the figures it is possible to find the value Nusselt numbers for a certain combination of heat transfer fluid and filler materials. For example, if we want to find the value of Nusselt number for Hitec salt and PCM H1 for discharging cycle we can find that it varies from 19.4 to 12.9. After 110 minutes the value becomes almost constant that means after 100 minutes the flow becomes fully developed.

Like charging cycle, it is also found that for a definite molten salt the Nusselt number starts from a single point and ends in a single line. The reason is same as the reason stated before. Nusselt number is a function of Reynolds number and Prandtl number, both of which are non-dimensional numbers that depend on temperature. So, all the values of Nusselt number of different PCMs as well as their combination show almost similar trends in the plot for a particular heat transfer fluid. At 0-minutes Nusselt number has a definite value because of the non-zero value of the Prandtl number at this moment.

From the figure 6.30 (a-c) it is also seen that some graphs have sharp transition from developing flow to developed flow while some figures have not. This may happen because of the effect of the thermophysical properties of phase change materials.

6.7 Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient for charging cycle

Figure 6.31: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Hitec salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.32: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Solar salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.33: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for FLiNaK salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.34 (a): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.34 (b): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Solar salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.34 (c): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for charging cycle

Interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) is the ratio of volumetric heat transfer coefficient to specific surface area and depends on porosity of bed, particle diameter and thermal conductivity. It is also proportional to the actual heat transfer coefficient. The higher value of IHTC is a sign of higher heat transfer between solid and fluid in porous media. If the heat transfer rate is higher less time is required to transfer heat. It is also a good indication of storing thermal energy inside solid particles. So, higher value of interstitial heat transfer coefficient is desirable.

Figure 6.31-6.33 show the interstitial heat transfer coefficient for different heat transfer media. Figure 6.31 show the result of interstitial heat transfer coefficient for Hitec salt. Figure 6.32 and Figure 6.33 represent the same for Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. This interstitial heat transfer coefficient is a function of the Nusselt number, particle diameter and thermal conductivity of filler materials. If thermal conductivity of filler materials increases interstitial heat transfer coefficient also increases. In the figure 6.31, it is seen that PCM H2, PCM H3 and solid rock have almost same value of maximum interstitial heat transfer coefficient. They have same thermal conductivity in solid and liquid phase except solid rocks as it is not a phase change material. So, it has only solid thermal conductivity. In a similar manner, the value of IHTC for PCM H1 is the lowest as it has the lowest thermal conductivity.

Highest values of IHTC are found for FLiNaK salt as the molten salt has the highest maximum temperature. Figure 6.33 (b) shows the interstitial heat transfer coefficient for PCM F2 which has the highest value of all the filler materials. In term of IHTC, the combination of FLiNaK salt and PCM F2 is the best choice to use as thermal energy storage.

It also depends on the temperature of hot fluid. For higher temperature of molten salt, the IHTC shows higher value. From the figure 6.34 (a-c), it can be observed that while solid rocks are used as filler materials, Solar salt has the higher value of IHTC than that for Hitec salt. Similarly, the value of IHTC for FLiNaK salt is higher than that of the Solar salt. Of the sets of figures, in the last figures, solid rocks are used as filler materials. So, all the properties of filler materials are the same for the three sets of figures. But in Figure 6.31 Hitec salt is used and the highest temperature of Hitec salt is less than that of the Solar salt. So, in Figure 6.31 (e) the highest value of IHTC is lower than that of the Solar salt which is demonstrated in Figure 6.31 (e). In a similar manner, as the maximum temperature is the highest for FLiNaK salt, there we have found the maximum value of IHTC.

6.8 Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient for discharging Cycle

Figure 6.35: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Hitec salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.36: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Solar salt using (a) PCM S1, (b) PCM S2, (c) PCM S3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.37: Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for FLiNaK salt using (a) PCM F1, (b) PCM F2, (c) PCM F3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.38 (a): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.38 (b): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for Solar salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.38 (c): Variation of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for dsicharging cycle

To use porous media for convective heat exchanger applications, one must estimate the interstitial heat transfer taking place between the solid and fluid phases. Naturally, the local thermal equilibrium assumption is discarded, and the two-energy equation model is used to determine the distinct temperatures of the fluid phase and solid phase, and the local interstitial heat transfer between the two phases. Thus, for engineering applications of porous media, the evaluation of the interstitial heat transfer coefficients is one of the important parameters.

In the discharging cycle, hot molten salt is taken out from the tank for external use. So, from another point of view discharging cycle also plays an important role. Because, if proper heat transfer does not occur heat will be wasted or maybe it takes more time to transfer heat. During discharging cycle, the value of interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) decreases with time. The reason behind it, as passes by cold fluid enters the tank the average temperature decreases and as the IHTC depends on temperature so the value of it decreases with time.

Interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) is also a function of thermal conductivity of filler materials. So, its value should change with the change of thermal conductivity. For this reason, we find that the heat transfer coefficients for FLiNaK salt are greater than the two other salts.

Figure 6.35-6.37 represent the interstitial heat transfer coefficient for discharging cycle. Figures 6.35, 6.36 and 6.37 show the result for Hitec salt, Solar salt, and FLiNaK salt respectively and each figure consists of five sub-figures. The sub figures are denoted by a, b, c, d and e representing PCM 1, PCM 2 PCM 3, three-stage PCM and solid rocks respectively. Lowest value is found for the combination of Hitec salt and PCM H1 as PCM 1 has the lowest thermal conductivity. In Figure 6.33 where Solar salt is used as heat transfer media PCM S3 has the highest value of IHTC. Similarly, in the Figure 6.37 where FLiNaK salt is the heat transfer fluid, we observe that PCM F2 shows the greatest performance.

Comparing the two figures, figure 6.34 (a-c) and figure 6.38 (a-c), it is found that the initial value of IHTC for discharging cycle is almost equal to the final value of IHTC. It should be equal unless heat is leaked or the average temperature decreases. In the discharging cycle, the value of IHTC reached a constant value and this final value of IHTC acts as an initial value for charging cycle. If heat is not wasted these two cycles continue their working, one after another.

6.9 Total enthalpy for charging cycle

Figure 6.39: Total enthalpy for Hitec salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.40: Total enthalpy for Solar salt using (a) PCM S1, (b) PCM S2, (c) PCM S3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.41: Total enthalpy for FLiNaK salt using (a) PCM F1, (b) PCM F2, (c) PCM F3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for charging cycle

Figure 6.42 (a): Variation of Total enthalpy for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.42 (b): Variation of Total enthalpy for Solar salt by using different filler materials for charging cycle

Figure 6.42 (c): Variation of Total enthalpy for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for charging cycle

Enthalpy, a property of a thermodynamic system, is the sum of the system's internal energy and the product of its pressure and volume. The total enthalpy of a system cannot be measured directly because the internal energy contains components that are unknown and not easily accessible. In practice, a change in enthalpy is the preferred expression for measurements at constant pressure because it simplifies the description of energy transfer. Enthalpy is an extensive property; it is proportional to the size of the system (for homogeneous systems). As intensive properties, the specific enthalpy $h = H / m$ is referenced to a unit of mass m of the system.

In this research, total enthalpy is defined as the summation of total enthalpy of fluid and total enthalpy of solid. Total enthalpy is not considered for the enthalpy whole tank rather it is the specific enthalpy of the system. But in this paper, it will be known as total enthalpy.

Figure 6.39-6.41 show the total enthalpy for different heat transfer media. Figure 6.39 show the result of total enthalpy for Hitec salt. Figure 6.40 and Figure 6.41 represent the same for Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. The value of total enthalpy increases with temperature as total enthalpy is a function of temperature. So, in an average the total enthalpy of Solar salt is greater than that of the Hitec salt. Similarly, the value of total enthalpy is the greatest when FLiNaK salt is used as heat transfer media. Again, from the figures, we observe that total enthalpy increases with average temperature of the TES tank and when the temperature becomes steady the total enthalpy of the tank also possesses a constant value.

In Figure 6.39 for the Hitec salt PCM H1 has the highest value of total enthalpy, and the value of it is 1772 kJ/kg. In Figure 6.40 where Solar salt is used as heat transfer media, PCM S3 shows the highest value of total enthalpy. In Figure 6.41, the highest enthalpy is found for the PCM F2 and the value is 3369 kJ/kg. Among all the combinations, the combination of FLiNaK salt and PCM F2 shows the greatest performance. So, it will be a suitable choice for charging cycle in term of total enthalpy.

From the figure 6.42 (a-c), it can be observed that the solid rocks have the worst value of total enthalpy though they require less time to achieve final position. In calculating total enthalpy, the temperature of heat transfer fluid and the thermal conductivity of filler materials play a vital role. Apart from these, latent heat of fusion, specific heat of fluid and solid have also perform a significant role in computation of the value of total enthalpy.

6.10 Total enthalpy for discharging cycle

Figure 6.43: Total enthalpy for Hitec salt using (a) PCM H1, (b) PCM H2, (c) PCM H3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.44: Total enthalpy for Solar salt using (a) PCM S1, (b) PCM S2, (c) PCM S3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.45: Total enthalpy for FLiNaK salt using (a) PCM F1, (b) PCM F2, (c) PCM F3, (d) three stage PCM and (e) solid rock for discharging cycle

Figure 6.46 (a): Variation of Total enthalpy for Hitec salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.46 (b): Variation of Total enthalpy for Solar salt by using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Figure 6.46 (c): Variation of Total enthalpy for FLiNaK salt using different filler materials for discharging cycle

Total enthalpy of discharging cycle is the key parameter for thermal energy storage tank. In the discharging cycle, hot molten salt is taken out from the tank for external use. Total enthalpy in the discharging cycle is important because the higher the value of total enthalpy in the discharging cycle the greater the heat can be used for external purpose. During discharging cycle, the value of total enthalpy decreases with time. The reason behind it, as time passes by cold fluid enters the tank the average temperature decreases and as the total enthalpy is a function of temperature, so the value of it decreases with time. For this reason, we find that the value of total enthalpy for FLiNaK salt is greater than the two other salts as FLiNaK has the highest value of maximum temperature.

Total enthalpy depends on internal energy and kinetic energy. Kinetic energy depends on flow velocity and internal energy ultimately depends on temperature. It is also a function of thermal conductivity, latent heat of fusion and specific heat of filler materials. So, its value should change with the change of this parameters.

Figure 6.43-6.45 represent the total enthalpy for discharging cycle. Figures 6.43, 6.44 and 6.45 show the result for Hitec salt, Solar salt, and FLiNaK salt respectively and each figure consists of five sub-figures. The sub figures are denoted by a, b, c, d and e representing PCM 1, PCM 2 PCM 3, three-stage PCM and solid rocks respectively. Comparing the figures 6.42 (a-c) and 6.46 (a-c) it can be seen that, the initial value of total enthalpy for discharging cycle is almost equal to the final value of total enthalpy of charging cycle. It should be equal unless heat is leaked, or average temperature goes down. In the discharging cycle, the value of total enthalpy reaches a constant value and this final value of IHTC acts as an initial value for charging cycle.

6.11 Comparison of Individual PCM Temperature

Figure 6.47: Progression of the different zones of the thermocline tank during the charge/discharge cycles

Figure 6.47 shows the progression of the different zones of the thermocline tank during the charging and discharging cycle. The storage process in the tank is described by different basic thermocline regions over the height of the tank. At the beginning of the charge cycle, the HTF passes through the inlet of thermocline tank and fills the packing area. Because of this, the energy exchange occurs between HTF and PCM(s) particles that lead to create a heat transfer region which can be called thermocline zone. This zone moves down along the tank during the charge cycle, leaving behind a high temperature zone and at the same time leads to increase the temperature of the zone below it. Therefore, the hot and cold regions can be defined as the upper and lower part of the tank, respectively.

Figure 6.48 (a-c) show the line diagram of temperature inside the TES tank using different filler materials for Hitec salt, Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively at 40 minutes during charging

cycle. Figure 6.48 (a) represents the line diagram for PCM H1, PCM H2, PCM H3, three stage PCM and solid rocks. All the temperature line start from a single line and this line represents the hot fluid temperature. For all the line diagrams, five distinct zones (figure 6.47) should be noticed however, one or two zones may be absent.

Figure 6.48 (a) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for Hitec salt during charging cycle

Figure 6.48 (b) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for Solar salt during charging cycle

Figure 6.48 (c) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for FLiNaK salt during charging cycle

The first zone is hot fluid zone which is present for all the line diagrams. Next, the pinch point interface zone comes where temperature decreases rapidly along tank height. For PCM H1, PCM

H2, PCM H3 and three stage PCM, this zone covers a little height of the latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) tank however, for solid rock, this zone covers almost 60% of the tank height. A phase change zone comes after the pinch point interface zone is seen inside the tank and in this zone, temperature shows steadiness for a time being. After this region a sub-solidus sensible heat zone is observed which is followed by the cold zone.

Figure 6.49 (a) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for Hitec salt during discharging cycle

Figure 6.49 (b) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for Solar salt during discharging cycle

Figure 6.49 (c) Tank temperature for different filler materials at 40 minutes for FLiNaK salt during discharging cycle

Pinch point interface zone, phase change zone and sub-solidus sensible heat thermocline zone altogether construct thermocline zone. The shape and position of the curve of different zones depend on the thermophysical properties, especially on the phase change temperature of the PCM particles. For the three-stage PCM, initially, at the top level of the tank, it follows the third PCM graph, then it follows the second PCM graph at the mid-level of the tank and finally, it corresponds to the first PCM graph.

Figure 6.49 shows the same plot for the discharging cycle. In the discharging cycle, cold fluid enters the tank from the bottom side of the tank and hot fluid is drained from the top of the tank. Here, also different thermal regions can be observed, however, for the graph of solid lines, no pinch point interface zone, phase change zone and sub solidus sensible heat transfer zone are observed, rather a only a big thermocline region is noticed.

6.12 Comparison of Charging and Discharging Time

Table 6.1 Charging and discharging time for different combinations of HTF and filler materials

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	Charging time, t (mins)	Discharging time, T (mins)
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	96	114
	PCM H2	85	71
	PCM H3	130	70
	Three Stage PCM	92.5	77
	Solid Rocks	72	74
Solar Salt	PCM S1	69.5	88
	PCM S2	86	79
	PCM S3	203	112
	Three Stage PCM	118	79
	Solid Rocks	77	85
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	87	205
	PCM F2	103	121
	PCM F3	118	76
	Three Stage PCM	91.5	142
	Solid Rocks	66	71

Figure 6.50: Charging time for different filler materials

Figure 6.51: Discharging time for different filler materials

Table 6.1 represents the charging time and discharging time for different combinations of the heat transfer fluid and filler materials. Figure 6.50 is the graphical representation of charging time whereas figure 6.51 shows the discharging time.

Charging time refers to the time when hot fluid fills up the whole tank. However, as hot fluid continuously transfers heat to the cold fluid there is no sharp indication that hot fluid replaces the whole cold fluid of the tank. Thus, it is difficult to find the actual time of charging and it is needed to define it. In this research, charging time is defined as the time when the average temperature of the TES tank reaches 0.1% below the hot fluid temperature and the discharging time is defined as the time when cold fluid reaches 0.1% above the cold fluid temperature. These two terminal temperatures are defined as charging terminal temperature and discharging terminal temperature respectively in this paper. The charging terminal temperatures are 499°C, 569.43°C and 746.235°C respectively, for Hitec salt, Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. On the contrary, these values for corresponding salt are 21.021°C, 280.28°C and 475.475°C respectively, for discharging cycle. From the average temperature vs time plot when the average temperature graph intersects the terminal temperature line, the corresponding time is the charging or discharging time.

From figure 6.50, the charging time of solid rocks are the lowest than all other PCMs. PCM H3, PCM S3 and PCM F3 have the highest charging time in the series of Hitec salt, Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. On the other hand, in the discharging cycle, PCM H1 has the highest discharging time in Hitec salt, PCM S3 has the highest discharging time for Solar salt and PCM F1 has the highest value of discharging time in FLiNaK salt. Like charging cycle here also found that the solid rocks have the lowest discharging time.

Charging and discharging time depends on many factors. One of the major factors is specific heat. Specific heat capacity is such a property of any material that can increase temperature on increasing the heat transfer to that material. In latent heat phase change materials (LHPCMs), two types of specific heat capacity are found: one is solid specific heat capacity, and another is liquid specific heat capacity. Generally, the value of liquid specific heat capacity is higher than that of the solid specific heat capacity of the same material. When a PCM starts to melt its temperature doesn't increase though heat is added to that material which also prolongs charging time. Furthermore, after melting higher specific heat capacity of PCM slower the slope of increasing temperature. So, it is found that the charging and discharging time are longer for phase change materials than that of the solid rocks.

6.13 Thermocline Thickness

Table 6.2 Thermocline thickness during charging cycle

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	$y(T_{max})$ m	$y(T_{min})$ m	Thermocline thickness during charging, W_{TC} (m)
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	0.88	0.27	0.61
	PCM H2	0.81	0.18	0.63
	PCM H3	0.88	0.17	0.71
	Three Stage PCM	0.88	0.17	0.71
	Solid Rocks	0.86	0.23	0.63
Solar Salt	PCM S1	0.77	0.22	0.55
	PCM S2	0.82	0.24	0.58
	PCM S3	0.94	0.32	0.62
	Three Stage PCM	0.95	0.23	0.72
	Solid Rocks	0.96	0.10	0.86
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	0.84	0.37	0.47
	PCM F2	0.88	0.43	0.45
	PCM F3	0.90	0.36	0.54
	Three Stage PCM	0.89	0.37	0.52
	Solid Rocks	0.91	0.00	0.91

Figure 6. 52: Thermocline thickness of different combinations for charging cycle

Table 6.3 Thermocline thickness during discharging cycle

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	$y(T_{max})$ m	$y(T_{min})$ m	Thermocline thickness during discharging, W_{TC} (m)
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	0.78	0.09	0.78
	PCM H2	0.82	0.21	0.82
	PCM H3	0.75	0.21	0.75
	Three Stage PCM	0.82	0.09	0.82
	Solid Rocks	0.85	0.10	0.85
Solar Salt	PCM S1	0.84	0.18	0.84
	PCM S2	0.77	0.20	0.77
	PCM S3	0.58	0.11	0.58
	Three Stage PCM	0.77	0.17	0.77
	Solid Rocks	0.92	0.04	0.92
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	0.74	0.06	0.74
	PCM F2	0.62	0.09	0.62
	PCM F3	0.57	0.17	0.57
	Three Stage PCM	0.64	0.05	0.64
	Solid Rocks	1.00	0.06	1

Figure 6. 53: Thermocline thickness of different combinations for discharging cycle

Table 6.2 and table 6.3 represents the thermocline thickness inside the TES tank during charging cycle and discharging cycle respectively for different combinations of HTF and filler materials. $y(T_{max})$ and $y(T_{min})$ are the positions of maximum and minimum temperature inside the TES tank. In charging cycle, $y(T_{max})$ is positioned above the position of minimum temperature while in discharging cycle, $y(T_{min})$ is positioned above the position of maximum temperature. W_{TC} is the difference between the maximum and minimum temperature positions.

Figure 6.52 and figure 6.53 are the graphical representations of thermocline thickness along tank height during charging and discharging cycle respectively. Thermocline refers to the junction temperature of hot and cold fluid with the variation of temperature from hot fluid to cold one. Thermocline thickness is the thickness of that thermal variation inside the fluid and the thickness depends on the thermal resistance, in other words, how much heat flow is resisted from hot fluid to colder one.

In figure 6.52 for Hitec salt PCM H1 has the lowest value of thermocline thickness with a thickness of 0.61m. For solar salt PCM S1 has a thermocline thickness of 0.55m and for FLiNaK salt PCM F2 has the thermocline thickness of 0.45m respectively and these values are the lowest for corresponding salts.

From figure 6.53 PCM H3, PCM S1 and PCM F3 has the lowest value of thermocline thickness for Hitec salt, Solar salt and FLiNaK salt respectively. The lowest thickness for the corresponding filler materials is 0.75m, 0.58m and 0.57m respectively. Smaller thermocline thickness is more desirable than large one. Because if the thermocline thickness is small, less heat will be transferred from hot fluid to relatively colder one.

6.14 Comparison of IHTC

Table 6.4 Value of IHTC for charging and discharging cycle at 210 mins

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	IHTC for charging cycle at 210 mins W/ (m ² . K)	IHTC for discharging cycle at 210 mins W/ (m ² . K)
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	170.78	145.33
	PCM H2	253.14	200.97
	PCM H3	253.14	200.97
	Three Stage PCM	225.69	182.42
	Solid Rocks	253.14	200.97
Solar Salt	PCM S1	266.07	218.42
	PCM S2	266.07	218.42
	PCM S3	349.15	271.45
	Three Stage PCM	293.77	236.10
	Solid Rocks	266.07	218.42
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	406.65	320.60
	PCM F2	412.3	324.07
	PCM F3	394.16	312.75
	Three Stage PCM	404.37	319.13
	Solid Rocks	298.2	249.14

Figure 6.54: Comparison of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for charging cycle

Figure 6.55: Comparison of Interstitial Heat Transfer Coefficient (IHTC) for discharging cycle

Table 6.4 shows the values of interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) for charging and discharging cycle at 210 minutes for all the combinations of heat transfer fluids and filler materials. From previous figures it can be seen that at 210 minutes interstitial heat transfer coefficient have a stable value. Three sets of data are presented separately in the table as well as individually plotted in the graph. Figure 6.54 shows the graphical representation of IHTC for charging cycle at 210 minutes and Figure 6.55 shows the result for discharging cycle at 210 minutes. For the first set, PCM H2, PCM H3 and solid rock have the same value of interstitial heat transfer coefficient as their thermal conductivity are same. In the second set where solar salt is used as heat transfer fluid, PCM S3 shows the highest value of IHTC because it has the highest value of thermal conductivity at 210 minutes for both charging and discharging cycle. In the final set, for FLiNaK salt PCM F2 has the largest value of IHTC. The reason is same; the value of thermal conductivity is the key element to influence the value of IHTC.

So, the value of IHTC is a function of thermal conductivity of filler materials. The higher value of heat transfer coefficient refers to the higher rate of heat transfer between heat transfer fluid (HTF) and filler materials. This higher rate of heat transfer is a good indication of total energy storage in the tank. The higher the value of the interstitial heat transfer coefficient the greater the amount of total heat stored inside the tank.

6.15 Comparison of Total enthalpy for charging cycle

Table 6.5 Value of total enthalpy for charging cycle

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	Enthalpy at t=0 mins kJ/kg	Enthalpy at t=210 mins kJ/kg	Difference kJ/kg
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	529	1772	1207
	PCM H2	473	1601	1136
	PCM H3	488	1666	1195
	Three Stage PCM	496	1679	1179
	Solid Rocks	582	1469	888
Solar Salt	PCM S1	623	1746	1116
	PCM S2	643	1815	1176
	PCM S3	730	2270	1613
	Three Stage PCM	666	1944	1301
	Solid Rocks	772	1647	874
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	1465	3192	1637
	PCM F2	1675	3369	1676
	PCM F3	1615	2966	1329
	Three Stage PCM	1585	3175	1548
	Solid Rocks	1538	2518	980

Figure 6.56: Value of Total Energy at t=210 mins for charging cycle

Figure 6.57: Comparison of Total Energy difference for charging cycle

Table 6.5 shows the value of total enthalpy for charging cycle at 0 mins and 210 mins for all the combinations of heat transfer fluid and filler materials. At 0 minutes the total enthalpy has minimum value and at 210 minutes the total enthalpy has the maximum value. Three sets of data are presented separately in the table. Figure 6.56 shows the graphical representation of total enthalpy for charging cycle at 210 minutes and Figure 6.57 shows the difference of total enthalpy for charging cycle. In the first set PCM H1 has the highest value of total enthalpy difference. In the second set where solar salt is used as heat transfer fluid, PCM S3 shows the highest value of enthalpy difference. In the final set, for FLiNaK salt PCM F2 has the largest value of total enthalpy difference, and it has the maximum value of total enthalpy at 210 minutes for charging cycle.

Enthalpy difference is the difference of total enthalpy at 0 minutes and 210 minutes. It indicates how much energy will be stored during charging cycle. If the value of enthalpy difference is higher, more heat will be stored. Obviously, stored energy depends on size of the tank. However, for same tank size it also depends on other parameters such as thermal conductivity, density, latent heat of fusion, specific heat capacity, difference between charging temperature and melting temperature etc.

6.16 Comparison of Total enthalpy for Discharging cycle

Table 6.6 Value of total enthalpy for discharging cycle

Heat Transfer Fluid	Filler Materials	Enthalpy at t=0 mins kJ/kg	Enthalpy at t=210 mins kJ/kg	Difference kJ/kg
Hitec Salt	PCM H1	1820	613	1243
	PCM H2	1629	493	1128
	PCM H3	1700	505	1178
	Three Stage PCM	1716	537	1183
	Solid Rocks	1469	581	887
Solar Salt	PCM S1	1767	651	1123
	PCM S2	1843	667	1172
	PCM S3	2452	839	1540
	Three Stage PCM	2020	719	1278
	Solid Rocks	1646	772	875
FLiNaK Salt	PCM F1	3292	1655	1727
	PCM F2	3482	1806	1694
	PCM F3	2894	1565	1351
	Three Stage PCM	3223	1675	1590
	Solid Rocks	2518	1538	980

Figure 6.58: Value of Total Energy at t=210 mins for discharging cycle

Figure 6.59: Comparison of Total Energy difference for discharging cycle

Table 6.6 shows the value of total enthalpy for discharging cycle at 0 mins and 210 mins for all the combinations of heat transfer fluid and filler materials. At 0 minutes the total enthalpy has maximum value and at 210 minutes the total enthalpy has the minimum value. Three sets of data are presented separately in the table. Figure 6.58 shows the graphical representation of total enthalpy for discharging cycle at 210 minutes and Figure 6.59 shows the difference of total enthalpy during discharging cycle. In the first set PCM H1 has the highest value of total enthalpy difference. In the second set where solar salt is used as heat transfer fluid, PCM S3 shows the highest value of enthalpy difference. In the final set, for FLiNaK salt PCM F1 has the largest value of total enthalpy difference, and it has the maximum value of total enthalpy at 210 minutes for discharging cycle. The nearest competitor of PCM F1 is PCM F2 and the value of enthalpy difference of PCM F2 is slightly lower than that of the PCM F1.

Enthalpy difference in the discharging cycle has great importance. It indicates that how much energy can be utilized by using stored energy. If the value of enthalpy difference in the discharging cycle is higher, more heat can be used for outside purpose. Higher enthalpy is desired after charging cycle and lower enthalpy is desired after discharging cycle. So, the difference will be higher for both charging and discharging cycle.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

The current work presents a two-dimensional, transient model of a thermocline thermal energy storage tank and analyzes its thermal performance. The model is validated against the published literature that ensures the acceptance of the results obtained from the study. Three types of molten salts are used as heat transfer fluid (HTF) and different types of phase change materials (PCM) and solid rocks are used as filler materials. The PCMs are selected in such a way that their melting point should be between the melting point and boiling point of heat transfer fluid. Thermophysical properties, availability and market price are the main criteria in the selection of PCMs. Total 30 simulations have been run and the results are discrete into two major parts; one is charging cycle, and another is discharging cycle. Variations of temperatures with tank axial distance for different time intervals are illustrated here from where the pattern of temperature distributions inside the tank can be understood easily. Nusselt number is plotted against time and the observation asserts that the Nusselt number depends on temperature. So, for a definite salt, all the phase change materials and solid rock have the same initial value of Nusselt number. Similarly, the terminal value of this number is the same for a definite molten salt. Interstitial heat transfer coefficients (IHTC) are plotted against time and the results show that the value is a strong function of thermal conductivity of filler materials. Velocity profile, pressure contour and streamline indicate the flow pattern of the molten salt. Total enthalpy (which is introduced in this paper as the summation of specific enthalpy of HTF and filler materials) are also plotted against time. All the graphs are plotted both for charging and discharging cycle. Finally, a brief comparison has been made based on IHTC and total enthalpy difference during a cycle. The whole study is performed for three

different temperature ranges of hot and cold fluids. Hitec salt works at the lowest temperature, solar salt at moderate temperature and FLiNaK salt at a higher temperature. Though their working temperature is different from each other, the difference in temperature is equal for all the molten salts and that is 290°C. So, it can be compared that, within the same temperature range which filler material perform the best.

The findings and outcomes of this research are listed below:

1. The flow is laminar inside the tank and the pressure is almost uniform except near the entrance of the tank where the pressure slightly higher.
2. The Nusselt number is relatively smaller, so the heat transfer is occurred by both conduction and convection.
3. Interstitial heat transfer coefficient (IHTC) is a strong function of thermal conductivity of filler materials and its value increases with the increase of thermal conductivity.
4. At elevated temperature the value of IHTC and stored energy is higher than that of the lower temperature.
5. For a definite temperature range total specific enthalpy depends on the thermophysical properties of filler materials like thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, latent heat of fusion etc.
6. Solid rocks require less charging and discharging time, as they are not associated with phase change phenomenon.
7. On the other hand, solid rocks have bigger thermocline thickness than phase change materials. So, heat can be transferred more easily from hot to cold fluid than any other filler materials.
8. Heat storage with phase change materials (PCMs) show better performance than that of the normal sensible heat storage materials.
9. Stored energy depends on the size of the thermocline thermal energy storage (TES) tank and if the size of the tank is increased the total energy will also be increased.
10. The output result obtained from Hitec salt is good, result obtained from solar salt is better and that is the best for FLiNaK.
11. In terms of enthalpy difference, PCM H1 performs good in Hitec salt and PCM S3 performs good in the solar salt, for both charging and discharging cycle.

12. PCM F2 performs good in the FLiNaK salt during charging cycle and PCM F1 performs good during discharging cycle.

It is also explored different thermophysical properties of heat transfer fluid and filler materials from the existing literature and tried to find the best mathematical correlation of thermophysical properties. From the above analysis, it can be realized that larger value of stored energy is found for higher temperature. The difference between the charging temperature of HTF and the melting point of the PCM also influences the heat transfer. The numerical approach, choosing the combination of PCMs and heat transfer fluid and their thermal analysis especially the effect of Nusselt number, interstitial heat transfer on time is unique from any other work of research. From this viewpoint, the thesis may be considered inimitable and different from other research works. By improving thermal properties like specific heat capacity and the thermal conductivity of filler materials this investigation will open the door to new research in this field. However, this work helps us to uncover a new horizon for storing thermal energy which governs us to harness more energy from sunlight by using a concentrated solar collector.

Chapter 8

Recommendation and Future Scope

8.1 Recommendation

From the above study it is recommended that,

1. Use high temperature hot fluid as filler materials. Because, If the charging temperature is higher stored energy will be higher.
2. Use large temperature difference between hot and cold fluid. If the temperature difference is higher, difference of total enthalpy will be higher. But it should be in a reasonable range.
3. Use FLiNaK salt as heat transfer fluid, if not possible then go for solar salt and if it is also unfeasible then use Hitec salt.
4. Use PCM F2 or PCM S3 as both are same filler materials.
5. Among all the combinations, the combination of FLiNaK salt and PCM F2 is recommended as PCM F2 has better heat transfer rate in both charging and discharging cycle, better heat storage capacity in charging cycle and it requires less time to reach final temperature.
6. Finally, the combination of solar salt and PCM S3 is also recommended, as PCM S3 (which is nothing but used as PCM F2 in FLiNaK salt) shows the significant performance though the temperature of solar salt is less than that of the FLiNaK salt.

8.2 Future Research Scopes

This present study is well documented and data intensive. The research has hopefully developed our understanding of the flow field, thermal fields, and performance parameters of two-dimensional, incompressible laminar flow inside a TES tank. So, a great amount of investigation is required to provide more to the following issue. The future scopes of the present study are summarized as follows:

1. More study on different types of heat transfer fluids and filler materials is required.
2. Study is required to develop the thermophysical properties of different types of inorganic salts and salt mixtures.
3. Optimization of thermal properties should be performed by simulation to get maximum storage capacity.
4. Cost analysis of the whole system should be made including initial cost and maintenance cost.
5. The investigation can be extended for three-dimensional steady and unsteady cases.
6. Experimental study of this type of problem is an urgent need

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